

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE)
Call: H2020-MSCA-RISE-2019

Grant Agreement n° 873082

CONTESTED_TERRITORY

**From Contested Territories to alternatives of development:
Learning from Latin America**

Deliverable 3.2:

Working Paper 2

Comparative Critical Policy Analysis applied to Territorial Accumulation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement No 873082.

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1. DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

Work Package	WP3 Documenting and visualising Contested Territories
Deliverable	D3.2: Working Paper 2 – Comparative Critical Policy Analysis about territorial accumulation
Due Date	M28: 31 December 2022
Submission Date	M28: 31 January 2023
Dissemination Level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU – Public
Deliverable Lead	La Hidra
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Status	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Approved internally
Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This working paper presents a diverse range of methodological and theoretical approaches to the critical analysis of policy mechanisms implicated in territorial accumulation in Latin America and Europe. The paper reviews various fields of relevance for critical policy analysis including policy mobilities; infrastructure investments; green and blue infrastructure and urban environmental policies in general; metropolitan growth and urban-rural conflicts; and Indigenous and Afro-American perspectives to territorial governing.
Keywords	Territorial Accumulation, Critical Policy Analysis, Public Policies, Policy Mobility, Infrastructure Regimes, Environmental Discourses, Other Knowledges

2. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This working paper presents a diverse range of methodological and theoretical approaches to the critical analysis of policy mechanisms implicated in territorial accumulation in Latin America and Europe. The paper reviews various fields of relevance for critical policy analysis including policy mobilities; infrastructure investments; green and blue infrastructure and urban environmental policies in general; metropolitan growth and urban-rural conflicts; and Indigenous and Afro-American perspectives to territorial governing.

3. FOREWORD

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This working paper has been prepared by the Critical Policy Analysis (CPA) working group, which began in the year 2020 right after the launch of the Contested Territory network and in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. Members from different research centres and social organizations participating in the network from Latin America and Europe have been meeting first online and then also in person, through secondments, with the aim of contributing to this theme and producing this document.

The discussions presented herein reflect this work in progress and provide an indication of the network's future outputs, including scientific and dissemination publications and policy briefs. In our first year of existence, the CPA group held three formative meetings in which various members presented research advances across the three following fronts: 1) methodological innovation for critical policy analysis; 2) the 'policy mobilities' perspective; and 3) the importance of policy networks, policy conditioners and social resistances to global policy-making. At these meetings two cross-cutting questions emerged. Namely, what do we understand by CPA? And what is the Contested Territory project's original contribution to this field?

On these concerns, we have focused on de-naturalizing power relations, taking "other knowledges" into account, and problematizing the economic models that commonly underpin policy analysis. The network's publication of Working Paper 3.1 on the dynamics of 'territorial accumulation' provided a theoretical framework for our group to update our discussions. This framing incorporates notions from political economy (Harvey), feminism (Federicci), decolonial studies (Williams, Mignolo) and world ecology (Moore). As such, territorial accumulation provides a critical reading of the multidimensional crises that global capitalism faces and how it attempts to restructure through spatial fixes, accumulation by dispossession and new forms of extraction. Territorial accumulation provides a way of understanding what is new in these operations of capital that less integrative literatures miss.

The critical analysis of policies helps us account for their role as mechanisms of territorial accumulation but also unveils the contestation that surrounds them. The diverse contributions included herein show that these politics need to be situated with various fields of power struggles between different interest groups, institutional and social structures, and historical and cultural contexts. From this perspective, our aim is to better understand how (contested) policies may promote or hinder extractivist and exploitative forms of development in specific territories. Such CPA relies on the critical review of policy documents and contrasting their content with qualitative empirical research conducted with policy makers, think tanks and NGOs.

In our various meetings we observed that the diversity of our contributors' methodological perspectives, theoretical framings, and the research contexts where they work provide major opportunities for comparative analysis in the policy mechanisms involved in territorial accumulation and its multiple contestations. This working paper brings together these perspectives into one document as a first step towards the formulation of comparativist strategies and techniques. Our aims are to understand why and how the policy mechanism of territorial accumulation produce different outcomes across various territories; how these outcomes can be better understood through relation and multi-scalar perspectives; and what methodological innovations can result from such broadly defined project, including potential complementarities between ethnographic approaches and quantitative analysis.

The sections that follow show that our members have explored questions pertaining to CPA across different fields of research including policy mobilities; the policy regimes conditioning infrastructure provision; the 'environmental' dimension of policy and the growing governmental interest in 'blue and green infrastructure'; the problematic construction of urban-rural differences across metropolitan edges; contrasts between market-centric and popular forms of logistics and provision; and the contestations to territorial accumulation that emerge from the claims of indigenous peoples, Afro-descendants and other groups historically excluded from the policy process.

We thank each and every contributor to this document and hope that its discussions may be of interest to those concerned with CPA both within and without our network.

Miguel Kanai, Carolina Gonzalez Redondo and Maria Florencia Marcos,
Coordinators of the Critical Policy Analysis group

4. COMPARATIVE DIMENSIONS IN PUBLIC POLICY: GLOBAL URBAN STUDIES, POLICY MOBILITY, MULTIPLE CASE DESIGN

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This section elaborates on some epistemological ideas and methodological approaches that cut across, and broadly inform, the comparative dimensions of Critical Policy Analysis in this working paper and, more broadly, within project Contested Territories.

Following a funnel-down structure, from the conceptual to the epistemological and the methodological, and from the general to the particular, the section is organised in three sections: we start, first, by discussing the contribution to comparative research brought forward in recent discussions in global urban studies; then, second, we move to consider the field of policy mobilities, its understanding of travelling policy ideas/practices and its potential for our analysis; finally, third, we zoom into the implications of case study research for comparative analysis, including by considering strategies for theorisation from single/multiple case/s.

4.1. Comparison and global urban studies

In broad terms, the comparative lens that we are interested in mobilising needs to go beyond the traditional idea of ‘comparability’ and the static observation of similarities and differences. On the one hand, the critical edge we are aiming to develop for the study of territorial accumulation and contestation needs to be informed by a historical sensibility – the understanding that there is a historical contingency to socio-economic relations and the refusal to accept things as they ‘naturally’ are. On the other hand, the global nature of our interests, together with the attention at developing post- and de-colonial re-theorisations, push us to focus on flows and connections: vertical (multi-scalar dimensions of urbanisation and territorial restructuring) and horizontal (social, cultural, economic and political flows among places).

We find promising conceptual and epistemological lenses in these directions in the recent development of so-called global urban studies, which have precisely worked toward a (re-)theorisation of the urban through the lenses we are interested in mobilising.

Before moving forward, a brief caveat is necessary to note that the conceptualisation of the ‘urban’ that this field has been working on – and that matches our goals – goes beyond that of the ‘city’ as an identifiable morphological character, rather considering the processes of socio-spatial transformation that broaden and inter-connect the ‘urban’ with their hinterlands and well beyond. We refer, in particular, to the debates on concepts like planetary urbanisation (Brenner & Schmid, 2015; Wilson and Bayón 2016), extended urbanisation (Keil, 2018), peri-urban developments (Kanai & Schindler, 2022), but also broader discussions on the urban’s constitutive outside (Roy, 2016) and the emerging Urbanocene (Mendieta, 2019).

Of particular use for our purposes are the insights by Jennifer Robinson (2016; 2022; see also *Urban Studies*, volume 59, issue 8), who has built on the recent flourishing of comparative exercises to explore the potentialities of the comparative gaze for, and beyond, urban studies, proposing two modalities for ‘tactics’ of conceptualisation.

In ‘generative’ tactics, ‘a virtual field of conceptualization can be provoked and enriched through bringing different singularities, or cases, into conversation’ (2016, p. 18). What characterises generative tactics, in other words, is the use of various cases to build and provide nuance to a conceptual argument or theory – the starting point can be a single case or rather a theory, and the comparative exercise is operationalised by testing and refining the conceptual framework in other cases, and so forth.

‘Genetic’ tactics, instead, start from (vertical or horizontal) interconnections and flows: ‘a range of comparative possibilities emerge in the practice of tracing the prolific interconnections amongst urban territories and working with the wider processes shaping urbanisation and urban outcomes’ (Robinson, 2022). The starting point, in other words, are not individual or multiple cases, rather the very connections among cases – Ricardo Cardoso (2022), for instance, traces the ‘lineaments of a Southern Atlantic urbanism’ by following the connections among urban developments in Salvador de Bahia (Brazil) and Luanda (Angola)

Because they move further away from traditional comparative approaches, Robinson additionally discusses how genetic tactics can articulate theoretical perspectives prominent in urban studies: on the one hand, ‘materialities perspectives’ (which include, for instance assemblages or actor-network theories), for their potential in ‘attending closely to connections and flows’ (2022, p. 1524); on the other, political economic perspectives, with their potential in attending to wider/global/structural processes and how different cases are embedded within extensively spreading socio-political and socio-economic formations (idem, p. 1526).

In this working paper, and more broadly within Contested Territories, this articulation is operationalised through multi-scalar and relational approaches (Souza, 2019; Tulumello, 2022), which are necessary to attend to the types of connections and conceptualisations underpinned by territorial accumulation and contestation. This is the case of our contributions enquiring on infrastructural development as a paradigmatic example of connection among global supply chains, local effects and grassroots infrastructures (Section 6 by Kanai et al.; Section 8 by Blanco et al.); the exploration of extractive forms of planetary urbanisation that mobile policies support (Section 5 by Giannotti et al.); and of the use of multi-locality and multi-territoriality as lenses to capture territorial practices of indigenous peoples (Section 10 by Horn et al.).

4.2. Policy mobilities – neoliberalism and beyond

The comparative gesture captured in this document is first and foremost mobilised through the epistemological lens of policy mobility/ies, a field that has been developed starting from the empirical observation of the diffusion, and the variegated geographical spread, of neoliberal governmentalities, thus contributing to making sense of the complex – and often contradictory and paradoxical (see Tulumello, 2016) – patterns of neoliberal (urban and territorial) policies (see Brenner et al., 2010; Peck, 2013).

In particular, policy mobilities look at the role of the circulation of policy ideas and practices in the processes of neoliberalisation, at the same time going beyond the simple model of irradiation from the centre toward the periphery/ies. In a seminal paper, Jamie Peck (2011) identifies three channels of policy mobility: first, the active role of transnational power networks that (intentionally) promote policy circulations; second, the way policy decisions taken in a place influence those of other places another – an influence that is partially, but not exclusively, shaped by the different positionings of the places of origin and reception in global geographies of power; and, third, the emergence of policy models that get codified for replication (often labelled as ‘best practices’).

Peck additionally notes how the study of policy circulation has developed from a modernist conceptualisation of transfer, which seems to be increasingly rare, to mobility, which implies adaptation, and even mutation, whereby the process of transformation is paramount, producing new policy arrangements in the process.

These triads have an heuristic role but, the following chapters will show, policy circulations always imply hybrid models. This is the case, for instance, of the interactions and reproductions among public policies guided by Western legal discourses, and often promoting territorial accumulation, and indigenous and Afro-American epistemologies and lived experiences, at times reproducing the same logics (Section 10 by Horn et al.); of the use of creative policies for building local coalitions, which problematises the simple idea of an exportation of policy models (from the North to the South) (Section 5 by Giannotti et al.); and of the complex arrangements

in the incorporation of the ‘environmental’ in urban policies and territorial accumulation (Section 9 by Gallardo Araya et al.).

Additionally, policy mobility is always captured as a policy struggle, that is, beyond the power imposition ‘from the centre and from above’, also in the dialectical role of territorial contestations. This is the case, for instance, of the relationships between infrastructural policies and popular habitats (Section 8 by Blanco et al.) and of the mobility of struggle in transnational mobilisations and activist networks (Section 5 by Giannotti et al.).

4.3. Case study selection and theorisation

In line with broader trajectories of urban studies and human geography, this document builds on case study analysis – integrated by mixed qualitative methodologies – as the core epistemological instrument. In order to fully exploit the potential of case study analysis for building multi-scalar causal and relational arguments, we broadly follow Bent Flyvbjerg’s insights (2006) on the strategy of case selection and the implications for theorisation. In line with our broader approach, the type of cases have been selected in terms of the connections under investigation: vertical connections (e.g., local cases that deviates from processes pushed by global transformations) and horizontal connections (e.g. policy transfer, policy mutation and different expressions in different cases).

In the following chapters, ‘critical’ cases are the most common, while we can also find instances of ‘extreme’ and ‘paradigmatic’ cases. Among the critical cases, we find indigenous policies that reproduce the colonial urban/rural binary (Section 10’s contribution by Imilan & Hernandez); the contradictory pathways of Latin American countries in granting land rights and territorial autonomy compatible with indigenous practices and cosmogonies, at the same time as allowing and fostering territorial extraction and accumulation (Section 10’s contribution by Horn and Bayón). A European case study of the conflicts produced by metropolitan expansion (Section 7 by Contin). An ‘extreme’ case is allowed by the discussion of the measures put in place in the context of an epidemic urgency prescient of the Covid-19 pandemic, which have resulted in a stress test for policy rationalities and implementation (Section 9 by Gallardo Araya et al.). Finally, we find a paradigmatic cases of (neoliberal) policies in the commodification of food but also its contestation through popular markets and alternative food distribution practices (Section 11 by Calegaris et al.).

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5. THE MECHANISMS OF TERRITORIAL ACCUMULATION THROUGH THE LENS OF POLICY MOBILITIES

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In this paper we recover the policy mobility approach to understand and study the processes of territorial accumulation. To do this, we present some conceptual keys on policy mobility (section 1) and relate them to the conceptual field of territorial accumulation (section 2). Then, taking up findings from our own previous and ongoing research, we present – from the perspective of policy mobility – a series of hegemonic and counter-hegemonic policies, practices and discourses that allow us to illustrate the mechanisms of territorial accumulation in Latin America (section 3). We identify a series of dominant mechanisms in the processes of assembling, mobilizing and (de)territorializing policies in relation to territorial accumulation, such as the construction of transnational networks of actors, good practices, international rankings of cities and their attributes, benchmarking and storytelling, among others. We conclude our contribution with the description of some areas to continue investigating in future research (section 4).

5.1. Policy mobility: conceptual keys

The policy mobility approach – developed mainly in the English-speaking world (Hoyt, 2006; McCann and Ward, 2010; 2011; Peck, 2009; Peck and Theodore, 2010; Prince, 2010; Temenos and McCann, 2012) – distances itself from the more classical literature on the transfer, diffusion and circulation of policies (Porto de Oliveira and Pimenta de Faria, 2017; Jajamovich, 2017, 2018; Peck and Theodore, 2010) based on three particular premises. First, the circulation of policies are conceived as socially constructed processes in which actors located in academic, political and organizational fields of different scales intervene. Second, mobility is understood as a complex, nonlinear and dynamic process, through which policies mutate during their journeys, and acquire different characteristics according to each local (McCann and Ward, 2010; Peck and Theodore, 2010). Finally, from the relational and territorial approach (McCann and Ward, 2010), policy formulation is approached on two dimensions: in its dynamism and relationship with global knowledge circuits, produced in a relational geography focused on networks and flows (McCann and Ward, 2010); and, at the same time, in its fixed character and rooted in the place (McCann and Ward, 2010).

Mobility processes can involve a complex web of actors, socio-material aspects and discourses. Among the actors involved in the circulation of policies stand out planners, public policy makers, officials, technocrats from the cities that export models, as well as local actors that implement these policies, recovering assumptions and ideas from the models that are put into circulation (Delgadillo, 2014; González, 2011; Jajamovich, 2018; Novick, 2009; Sánchez and Moura, 2005; Vainer, 2014). Also central are the experts, consultants and international organizations that together make up the so-called “global consultocracy” (Saint Martin, 2000). This mobility is based on socio-material aspects that enable and condition displacements. The materials, technologies and circuits that support mobility processes – media, conferences, cooperation agreements between cities, workshops, study tours, policy tours, urban policy tourism, awards, etc. (González, 2011; McFarlane, 2011; Cook and Ward, 2012) – are not only a medium for circulation, but also shape policies and condition their mobility (Silvestre and Jajamovich, 2022).

Mobility processes are unequal and selective, not all ideas, discourses and models have the same possibility of travelling (McCann, 2011). In the selection of proposals that become mobile not only influence the networks of actors that mobilize them; but also the very nature of the models. The greater its elasticity and adaptability, the greater the possibilities of being associated with hegemonic ideas and discourses and thus building consensus and legitimacy for its implementation in various local contexts. Thus, the models that become more popular and hegemonize the academic and public management agenda also circulate as discursive formations (Saunier, 2002) that condition what can be said, thought and done in terms of urban policy. As Temenos & McCann (2012) warn, local arrangements are always “extra-local” in their construction and legitimation. Hence the importance of articulating the relational and territorial dimensions in the analysis of mobility processes by territorial accumulation mechanisms.

5.2. Policy mobility and territorial accumulation

While the classic studies of policy transfer in political science had a rather positivist epistemological focus, the policy mobility turn is anchored in critical theory, particularly critical geography (McCann and Ward, 2011). It aims to understand the circulation of ideas, discourses, and policies in relation to a historically specific mode of capitalist accumulation, neoliberalism, and has focused on understanding how neoliberal urban policies sustain accumulation in this phase of planetary urbanization (McCann and Ward, 2011). Notwithstanding, the accumulation mode approach has been rather implicit. What remains to be developed in this context - and this is where some of the aims of the Contested Territories project are situated – is to make explicit, conceptualize, and investigate the relationship between policy mobility and territorial accumulation in a broader sense, including but going beyond neoliberal urbanism.

As developed in Working Paper 1: Analytical Categories of Territorial Accumulation (Bayon et al 2022), territorial accumulation as a category of analysis refers to a synthesis of different conceptualizations at the intersection of ecological, postcolonial, feminist, and Marxist thought. that explain the advances of capital over people, territories and non-commodified nature. In essence, territorial accumulation implies the subsumption of territories under the logic of global capitalism, through its processes of violent abstraction, the production of second and third natures, and its racist and patriarchal colonial projects: “the territorialisation of capital is not only a process of accumulation, but also of repositioning the white-bourgeois elites over the indigenous and peasant peoples” (referencia??). On the other hand, the authors highlight that this same territorial accumulation produces processes and subjectivities that resist subsumption. What we can conclude is that there is a dialectical relationship and a constant movement between processes of deterritorialization and reterritorialization of the flows of capital, energy, matter, and ideas and subjectivities (Haesbaert, 2014).

Although the production and circulation of policies is also part of the tangled material and symbolic circuits that sustain or resist territorial accumulation, up to now this has not been sufficiently and comprehensively addressed, combining top-down and bottom-up perspectives. The literature on policy and knowledge circulation has focused more on models, experiences and ideas produced and mobilized from above and, currently, linked to expressions of neoliberal urbanism (Parnell & Robinson 2012). Fewer are the works that inquire into knowledge, models and experiences of resistance and contestation mobilized from below, by social organizations, civil society institutions, public officials, etc. (Massey, 2011). Likewise, in this field of work, the circulation of north-north and north-south experiences has been privileged; while fewer studies focus on south-south, south-north or intra-regional and national circulations (Jajamovich and Silvestre, 2022). Another gap within this field of studies refers to the circulation of ideas and knowledge mobilized by business actors; ideas that in turn shape their perceptions and strategies. Precisely for the understanding of contemporary material and immaterial processes and strategies of territorial accumulation and its contestation, it is key to understand the interface and complex interaction between the different flows, circulation networks and their actors. Lastly, it is worth mentioning that within the existing literature on the circulation of

policies, there is no proper territorial vision; that is, studies and conceptualizations that think urban and rural together and in their analyses combine spaces, networks, and urban and rural policies and how they are related to territorial accumulation. The following cases are based on research projects that illustrate how the theoretical approach of policy mobility can be applied in the critical analysis of spatial policies.

5.3. Case studies

5.3.1. *Industry clusters, creatives cities and megaprojects*

Within the framework of neoliberal urbanism, a number of policies facilitating territorial accumulation have been disseminated globally, such as industry clusters, creative cities and megaprojects that have circulated and produced relevant impacts in Latin American cities. The central assumption of the cluster notion is that the geographical concentration of companies and institutions in the same economic sector generates exchanges that favours the growth of the entire chain through the so-called synergies. It assumes it spills over into investment and employment and, in this way, drives development processes (Porter, 1998). Another assumption maintains that companies require competitive advantages for which not only what happens inside matters, but also the external “business climate”. Thus, the State - at all levels - must facilitate, identify and improve the competitive advantages of its territory that collaborate in the creation of a “business climate” (Porter, 1998).

Creative policies are another popular idea. Florida (2002) marked a milestone in the debate on creativity as a driving force for the economic development of cities (Peck, 2009; Scott, 2014). Florida's approach aims to promote suitable environments to channel and take advantage of the talent of the creative class. Thus, creativity became the new formula for urban growth and the already consolidated idea of generating “business climates” to attract mobile investment was covered with the new creative approach (Peck, 2009).

Buenos Aires' local government has actively promoted the establishment of economic districts (technological, artistic, design, audiovisual) through tax, financial and real estate incentives, and public investment oriented to urban renewal. Since 2009 it has selectively combined approaches from cluster models, creative economies and cities, and new urbanism (Gonzalez Redondo, 2022). First, technological district was created as an initiative to strengthen this industry, based on agreements between public officials and businessmen in the sector. To legitimize this policy locally, “successful” cases from other parts of the world were appealed to, such as 22@ Barcelona. Technological district –with its characteristics and adaptations- maintained only a symbolic relationship with its reference model. Later, it became a new model - adjusted to local possibilities- that circulated within the territory of the city of Buenos Aires and gave rise to other economic districts (Gonzalez Redondo, 2022). It was a gradual and hand-made process of local circulation of a model considered successful.

The analysis of the internal circulation of Buenos Aires districts sheds light on several aspects of the mobility processes: (1) even when they circulate within the same city and political management, the models produce adaptations; (2) internal mobility produces multiple legitimations: it legitimizes the new districts as well as supports the model that is put into circulation; (3) the inertia that policy mobility processes acquired leads to proliferation of policies that use the same models without being clear about the objectives or problems that they seek to address. Economic districts circulated as discursive formations that seduced professionals and officials, legitimising but also constraining public activity: framing problems and their possible solutions, as well as obstructing the possibility of formulating proposals based on the reading of the dynamics and processes of each territory.

Lastly, urban megaprojects are large-scale development initiatives aimed to achieve a comprehensive transformation of spaces in cities through changes in land uses and in the built environment. These are complex programmes of urban intervention involving multiple stake-

holders and employing substantial levels of capital. One strategic quality of urban megaprojects rests on its imaging effects. Flagship projects – often making use of iconic architecture and renowned architects – are employed as key symbols to confer a distinctive identity and project an instantly recognizable image to a global audience (Ponzini, 2020; Sklair, 2017). The redevelopment of waterfront areas is a conspicuous example and within Latin America there are clear cases of such practices and their social implications as seen with Buenos Aires' Puerto Madero, Rio de Janeiro's Porto Maravilha, and Guayaquil's Malecon 2000 programmes (Jajamovich, 2018; Silvestre, 2022).

Recent research has stressed the need to critically interrogate the role of domestic actors. This can overcome taken for granted power asymmetries in the flow of urban policy ideas, particularly in cases where cities in the Global North are presented as 'exporting sites' for a Global South market of 'importing sites'. Authors examining relational urban change from a Southern perspective have paid particular attention to the politics at the demand side and the instrumental use of policy models as a tool for building coalitions (Silvestre and Jajamovich, 2021).

5.3.2 *Extractivist urbanism*

Extractivist urbanism has recently become a relevant field for analysing urban policy mobilities. Although cities and urban infrastructural networks in Latin America since colonial times have been designed to sustain the extraction of gold and silver, nitrate and copper, oil and gas (e.g. Potosí, Belo Horizonte, Lago Agrio or Antofagasta), the practices and politics of extractivist urbanism have seldomly been addressed in systematic, relational and comparative ways (but see Correa, 2017). To advance toward a more comprehensive understanding of extraction in this age of the planetary mine (Gago and Mezzadra, 2017; Arboleda 2020, Chagnon et al, 2022), it is increasingly apparent that the links between extraction, old and new extractive industries, and urban space production have to be further explored (Wilson and Bayon, 2020; Lukas, 2022; Lukas and Brueck, 2018).

An intriguing example of the interaction of actors in the extractive industries with the global urbanist intelligence corps, resulting in novel discourses, practices, and power/knowledge in the urban domain, can be found in Chile. The social and environmental impacts of neo extractivist development in recent decades have resulted in wide-ranging social mobilisation questioning transnational companies and urban-environmental conflicts, forcing accused companies to re-evaluate their justification, community relations, and territorial strategies (Tironi, 2018; Devenin, 2019, Leiva, 2019). One outcome has been for these companies to enter the arenas of urban planning and governance (Lukas & Brueck, 2018). Global extractive companies including BHP Billiton, the Chilean Luksic and Angelini, and international architects, have worked together to create urban master plans. Public-private alliances have been established for, officially, enhancing quality of life, sustainability, and civic participation bringing together urbanists, storytellers, and engineering consultancies. The model was originally developed in response to an earthquake and tsunami in 2010 and has since been replicated and developed in other cities with socio-environmental emergencies, such as Calama, Antofagasta, Valdivia or Choapa. The actors in each initiative, the geographical setting, and the socio-environmental problem landscape (with McCann and Ward 2011 addressing the territorial aspect of the policy assemblage) are unique, but the initiatives are interconnected within them and connected outwards to actors and ideas outside of the local context who are involved in developing, framing and mobilizing the model (the relational aspect of the policy assemblage).

The following aspects are particularly noteworthy: (1) new associations between knowledge fields and their experts have been established; (2) initiatives are branded as best practices despite criticisms and failures of implementation; (3) international organisations and consultants play key roles for legitimising the initiatives, conducting benchmarking, also enhancing their international visibility (Lukas and Brueck, 2018; Lukas, 2022). Further research could focus on how individual initiatives and the model created are being de- and re-territorialized through the cultural-corporate circuits of the extractive industries beyond the Chilean case. It

is also relevant to ask which other territorial strategies extractive industries employ that guarantee the subsumption of territories under the logics of extractivist territorial accumulation.

5.3.3 The global new municipalism movement

The last decade was marked by global insurgent movements occupying public spaces to demonstrate their distrust in the political-economic order. Despite the variegated contexts that produced the Arab Spring, Occupy, the Spanish Indignados or the Chilean Social Outburst, these mobilisations used the urban space both as the stage and the catalyst for the formation of a collective identity questioning the dominant political-economic order (Briata et al, 2020). Such gatherings were triggered in many cases, by the struggles of everyday life in the city: repression of uses of the public space, the gentrification of neighbourhoods, the delivery of decent public services or the unaffordability of housing, that soon escalated to wider calls for better democracy and social equality. Despite their inchoate and large spectrum of grievances, these events constituted incipient political moments for their radical demand for systemic change rather than narrowly defined agendas (Dikeç & Swyngedouw, 2017). The challenge was to sustain the passage from urban social movements to urban political movements, thus moving ‘from outbursts of indignation to the slow process of sustained transformative strategies through which a new socio-political spatialization becomes imagined, practised, and universalized’ (Karaliotas & Swyngedouw, 2019: 378). One such sequence was for some groups to overcome their ambivalence towards ‘occupying’ political institutions and to ‘hack the state’ from inside out with new approaches to radical democracy.

The local scale is seen as a ‘strategic site for a transformative and prefigurative politics’ (Russell, 2019: 991). While it aims to enter institutional spaces and reorganise its structures and distribute power, this is to be coordinated with mobilisations from inside and outside the state boundaries with the potential to strengthen the recognition of social rights and develop new forms of governance for a more just city. Such experiences - including the creation of cooperatives, the remunicipalisation of privatised services and the incubation of social enterprises - are still nascent and marked by tensions and contestations (Thompson, 2021).

Despite the variegated contexts of such experiences there have been efforts to articulate a global ‘new municipalist’ movement aimed at forging translocal networks of solidarity and shared practices. The experience of the municipality of Barcelona has been the paradigmatic example and the chief coordinator of this movement since the organisation of a dedicated summit in 2017 and publishing a ‘Guide to the Global Municipalist Movement’ (Barcelona en Comú, 2019). The architecture of this global network currently encompasses more than 80 political organisations, digital observatories and regular summits. Academic analyses are still scarce and most focus on the most visible example of Barcelona. This points to the need for comparative studies capable of interrogating the constitutive experimentation through territorial municipal politics and the relational circulation of knowledge, as well as ‘crucial[ly] ... move beyond [the] limited North-Atlantic focus’ (Thompson, 2021: 335). Experiences in Latin American cities such as Rosario (Argentina), Valparaíso (Chile), and Belo Horizonte (Brazil) provide a locus for the examination of this movement as well as sites from which new municipalism is being shaped.

5.3.4 Transnational housing activism

Housing movements are usually born at the local level, from concrete experiences of struggle and resistance. There are several examples, that show the diversity of those movements, such as the pobladores movement in Chile (Angelcos & Pérez, 2017; Giannotti & Braithwaite, 2021; Herrera, 2018), the mobilization against eviction in Spain (Martínez & Gil, 2022; Romanos, 2014), the squatter movement in Berlin (Holm & Kuhn 2011; Vasudevan, 2015), or the homeowner associations in China (Ting et al., 2020; Yip, 2020), to mention just a few.

It is not unusual for local experiences to upscale into organizations which are able to expand their scope and establish networks with other similar organizations, nationally and internationally. The analysis of these housing processes must consider, from one hand, the regional differences between policies, civil societies and national institutions, and, from the other hand, the multiple levels and scales in which the housing activists operate (Herrle et al., 2016). While some authors have used the concept of networks, McFarlane (2009) has suggested conceptualizing the multi-scaled spatiality of these movements as “transnational assemblage”. This points to the importance of the process of collective construction, rather than the resultant formations. Moreover, he stresses “that translocal social movements are more than just the connections between sites” (p. 562).

Few studies have explored how ideas and knowledge circulate in regard to housing movements. Hölzl (2022) has examined the German Mietshäuser Syndikat and identified four main mechanisms for the production of networks and exchange of knowledge. First, a group of activists are the principal vector for the circulation of the model. Second, physical meetings facilitate the exchange of learning and contribute to the production of bridging social capital. Third, virtual meetings assure a continuous exchange. Finally, a range of toolkits, continuously updated, further facilitate the process of interchange. Hölzl concludes that those mechanisms helped to establish new experiences in other contexts but are not enough to bridge the inequalities in the allocation of resources and knowledge. This is partly due to the principle of volunteerism. For example, in case of uncertainty, key actors gave priorities to local activities over the international ones.

In the analysis of Liverpool’s collaborative housing models, Thompson (2017) highlights the importance of the social memories and resources embedded in place, together with circulating ideas and knowledge. To disentangle the complex interweaving between globally mobile ideas and place-based processes, the author proposes to complement the policy mobility approach with a planning history perspective.

Although there is an abundant literature about single experiences based, attempts to compare various cases are still scarce (Herrle et al., 2016; Lang et al., 2020; Martínez, 2020). It is also less frequent to find studies applying the policy mobility approach to the transnational housing movements and organisations. Future research should focus on the critical interrogation of international organisations, such as the Secretaría Latinoamericana de la Vivienda y el Hábitat Popular (SELVIHP), which brings together several Latin American organisations created to promote self-management of habitat, mutual aid and collective ownership (<https://selvihp.org>).

5.4. Areas for future research

The review of the current state-of-the-art and the cases illustrated here raise a number of key areas to be developed in future research. The following points provide potential directions for a comparative and relational programme in the circulation of knowledge and territorial accumulation:

- Relational analysis of processes of change, accumulation, and resistance

The application of a policy mobilities framework offers important analytical gains for critical policy analysis and studies of territorial accumulation. On the one hand, it allows greater depth to single case studies by transcending the particular context that explains spatial transformation and by positioning such change in relation to wider processes, agency and networks well beyond the boundaries of the sites of study. On the other hand, the grounding of such processes enables an understanding of how (neoliberal/extractive) capitalism materialises and in turn shapes understandings, practices and resistances in future interventions. Although there has been a fruitful production of academic interrogation based on the former approach, it remains scarce the analyses of how each individual process of territorial accumulation is formative to consequential interventions while generating a new round of network formation and knowledge circulation.

- Longitudinal analysis in the circulation of ideas: history, failure and forward travels

The policy mobilities literature has been criticised by its ‘presentism’ and ex-post analysis of ‘successful’ cases of policy and urban change. Recent studies have advocated the need for taking a longer view of the history of policy ideas (Baker and McCann, 2020; Ward, 2018) as well as for new rounds of circulation that can happen after they are grounded and mutate into strategies that can filter through wider territories (Silvestre and Jajamovich, 2022). This requires analyses of policy ‘failure’ to demonstrate the generative effects, incremental dynamics and ‘absent presences’ of policies that though may fail to materialise in the first instance, can steer policy debate and learning to open-ended pathways.

- Critical mapping of the circulation of ideas: coloniality, sites of production, agency involved

Latin America is a key region for the study of how circulating ideas, policies and practices of territorial accumulation were (violently) implemented, refined and re-circulated as well as resisted by socio territorial movements envisioning alternative futures (Halvorsen et al, 2019). The critical mapping and genealogy of hegemonic ideas can expose dominant practices of territorial accumulation that are rearticulated, despite changes in institutions, networks or imperialist projects. At a moment when Latin American decolonial thinking is being rediscovered (Asher, 2013; Maldonado-Torres & Cavouris, 2017) it also provides a strategic site for theory-building that can connect decolonial debates with policy mobilities and point toward the potential of alternative projects to emerge as well as circulate.

- Systemic interrogation of networks: linkages, capital switch, flows

Another fruitful area for intervention is the bridging between the urban extractivist turn and the policy mobilities literature. As described earlier in the text, cities have been increasingly targeted as sites for resource extraction as corporations switch their investment and expertise to new frontiers for capital and territorial accumulation. Mundane urban activities have also been reimagined as arenas for extractive practices by platform capitalism (Gago & Mezzadra, 2017). A systemic view of how the different circuits of extractivism operate and are integrated, require an analysis of their infrastructure (Arboleda, 2020) that can consider the informational infrastructures through which policy knowledge and templates circulate (Cook & Ward, 2012).

- Relational-comparative analysis between the networks of accumulation and resistance

The circulation of knowledge and practices within networks of territorial activism and resistance has received far less attention than hegemonic policy ideas. Despite the marked challenges in sustaining a structure for circulation in the long-run – as is the case of volunteerism and limited resources discussed earlier – they can have a global reach and connect agendas of solidarity that are crucial when windows of opportunity are open for systemic change. New place-based political platforms such as new municipalism offer the opportunity to investigate how local interventions are shaping as well as being shaped by the emergent global municipalist movement. The analysis of the movement is also relevant for comparing the dimensions of divergence and convergence in relation to hegemonic networks.

The points listed above inform the areas of investigation of the Working Group on Policy Mobilities of the Contested Territories project. Provisionally structured around hegemonic and counter-hegemonic networks of knowledge circulation it is analysing how neoliberal and extractivist projects have intensified in Latin America while examining more recent approaches of resistance and alternatives.

5.5. References

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6. INFRASTRUCTURE INVESTMENTS: SUPPORTING TERRITORIAL ACCUMULATION OR ITS ALTERNATIVES

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6.1. Introduction

In the twenty-first century, the provision of infrastructure has turned into a more prominent mechanism for territorial accumulation (Castro et al., 2022). Whilst deemed essential for economic development, infrastructural investments require critical examination for their potential environmental impacts and the social upheaval that projects often stir. Furthermore, varying conceptions of infrastructure are key for alternatives to development and economic globalisation to envision how territories could be materially supported and connected to the world otherwise. Promoting ‘infrastructure-led development’ in emerging economies of low- and middle-income countries figured largely among state responses to the 2008 global recession (Schindler and Kanai, 2021). Mitigating bottlenecks in logistics to facilitate trade, for example by upgrading road networks and interconnecting them across national borders, was the fix from supra-national organizations implicated in jump-starting the world economy (ibid.). Infrastructure became an area of increased concern for governmental and private institutions, including the World Bank, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), the crisis-originated G20, and the World Economic Forum (Kanai and Schindler, 2022). In its unprecedented role as a major international lender for infrastructure projects, the People’s Republic of China also participated in this approach but following its own strategies, interests and modes of engagement (Apostolopoulou, 2021). Large-scale transnational corporations, particularly those involved in extractive fields, also engage in the provision and management of infrastructure and logistics operations as part of their vertically integrated activities (Lukas, 2022). Many national governments across Latin America, Africa and Asia have willingly engaged in the resulting “scramble for infrastructure” by creating or repurposing ministries to plan, build or contract, and operate large-scale projects (Kanai and Schindler, 2019). Meanwhile, local responses have featured prominent protests, everyday resistances, and demands for alternative infrastructure futures, which makes for a complex and contentious infrastructural politics.

This section proposes an analytical framework and pathways to further examination for brick-and-mortar projects (both those actually built and those failing), the legal infrastructures that frame them, and the infrastructural discourses of legitimation. We focus on Latin America and seek to learn from the region’s complex politics of infrastructure, which straddle across diverse geographies of territorial contestation, from mega-urbanised cores to remote regional peripheries. If Latin America’s contested transition from post-neoliberal to extractivist political economies (Svampa, 2014) has relied on the articulation of “infrastructural circuits of extraction” and national governments have embraced “the promise of connectivity” whilst aligning policies to global mandates articulated around “connectivity as conditioner” (Kanai and Schindler, 2019); a “popular infrastructural politics” (Télez, 2020) has also emerged. This demands the making of “popular infrastructures” (Minuchin, 2021) and “popular logistics” (Minuchin and Maino, 2022) in support of social reproduction and everyday life. As grassroots infrastructural interventions, both are deeply rooted in the workings of local organisations and their struggles to secure the procurement of goods and services. The goal is to facilitate the reproduction and improvement of marginalised and vulnerable communities. By producing public and common infrastructures where solidarity structures can thrive, these material oppositions to territorial

accumulation animate a more “radical politics of infrastructure” (Vasudevan, 2015), that is supported by “technologies of liberation” (Rosati, 2019).

The section first develops the analytical terms to make sense of mechanisms promoting territorial accumulation and those opposing it whilst creating alternatives. Secondly, the section provides a concrete example of a corporate-led infrastructure initiative in Chile and the production of social public infrastructures and commoning platforms in Ecuador and Brasil. Thirdly, and in conclusion, it suggests methodological strategies for further comparative policy analysis of the multiple possible relations between infrastructure and territorial accumulation and reflects on the challenge of linking urban and rural struggles, which oppose a global model of territorial accumulation even if specifically mobilising against its highly localised manifestations.

6.2. The Rise of Infrastructure-led Development

The global discourse of the new structural economics has been highly influential in Latin America where infrastructure deficits are seen as a major bottleneck for economic growth and the state has been actively mobilised to fill this major ‘infrastructure gap’ (Lin, 2022; Hope, 2022). New or restructured state agencies have intervened at multiple levels to facilitate and promote foreign investments in large-scale infrastructure projects. For example, questions of infrastructure development have been included in both bi-lateral and multilateral free-trade and cooperation agreements, whilst national governments have re-engaged with regional planning and the long-forgotten attempt to connect ‘backward regions,’ which are now seen as valuable for extractivist networks (Kanai and Schindler, 2022). Whilst these plans are hailed as bringing new economic opportunity through improved infrastructure connectivity, they have also been shown to trigger socio-ecological devastation across various Latin American landscapes (Gordillo, 2019; Escobar, 2008; Arboleda, 2020); to introduce new threats for residents of conflicted-affected regions (Barrera et al., 2022); and to create peri-urban spaces characterised by their multiple precarities, which go unacknowledged in regional development plans failing to recognise the extended urbanisation effects of infrastructure corridors (Kanai and Schindler, 2022).

Alternative infrastructural practices have emerged from social groups in their struggles for social justice and environmental protection that they see essential for their survival and the ‘defense of life’ (Luna Nemecio, 2021). By designing and finding ways to finance and implement such infrastructures otherwise, these social actors seek to mitigate the resulting effects of intensified uneven development over already impoverished, excluded and vulnerable communities, and have produced new concepts that help re-think the potential role of infrastructure in contesting the operations of territorial accumulation. These concepts highlight the emancipatory potential of material infrastructures put at the service of social needs other than capitalist imperatives and broaden our socio-spatial horizons for collective action. As explained below, notions of commoning and the popular are key to understanding these alternatives.

When applied to infrastructure, commoning, or the co-creation of collective resources, can become a practice that forges and stabilises a set of new urban habits and habitats (Blok, 2016). For Amin (2014, p. 148), infra-commoning points to “an intricate play between the infrastructural aesthetic, social praxis and collective organization shaping the culture of the commons” in a particular locality. Thereby, infra-commoning foregrounds the collective work to consolidate a settlement by creating a communal landscape through agreed rules, public and shared spaces and environmental awareness. This is achieved through “services and spaces that are valued, summoning civic participation and care for the commons, and materially merging the private and the public” (ibid., p. 149). Solid waste, grey water and other sanitation plans, as well as lighting, greening and community centre and farm projects underpin a praxis that calls for solidarity, co-responsibility and a culture of knowledge sharing. Thus, infra-commoning produces infrastructural landscapes of “considerable symbolic power [that function] as a mnemonic of collective possibility” (ibid., p. 147).

Whilst processes of self-help or informal building take place around the world, the notion of the popular is of particular relevance for Latin America. Minuchin's (2021) notion of 'popular infrastructures' points to "a repertoire of socio-material adaptations that serve to stabilize an integrated network of programs and associations" (p. 5). Popular infrastructures may emerge as delayed incomplete construction projects, but also as the incremental interventions that reveal the numerous actors (committees, private developers, NGOs, local representatives) and the constantly adapted regulatory layers that prefigure urbanisation in peripheral settlements. These infrastructures are mediums that organise politics, projecting on to the landscape not a planned but a prefigured urbanisation and other models of territorial organisation, including the "counter-models" to government and private agendas (p. 9).

Based on the study of infrastructural practices in Monte Sinaí, Guayaquil, Ecuador, Leandro Minuchin advances the notion of "popular infrastructures." These "illustrate the workings and traces of urban subjectivities and give consistency to local organizations that demand a voice and presence in the urban future of Monte Sinaí" (Minuchin, 2021, p. 8). As infra-commoning, popular infrastructures crystallise socio-political relations; however, in this case such infrastructures emerge from . While popular infrastructures sustain alternative socio-spatial configurations, they also materialise the overlapping and competing urbanisation agendas that characterise settlement management in Latin America. In Monte Sinaí, popular infrastructures emerge as delayed, incomplete housing projects but also as the incremental interventions that reveal the numerous actors (committees, private developers, NGOs, local representatives) and the constantly adapted regulatory layers that prefigure urbanisation in peripheral settlements. These infrastructures are mediums that organise politics, projecting on to the landscape not a planned but a prefigured urbanisation and other models of territorial organisation, including the "counter-models" to government and private agendas (Minuchin, 2021, p. 9).

6.3. Case study (I): a vertically integrated extractive and logistic chain in Northern Chile

A fascinating example of the trend toward vertical integration and monopolistic control of infrastructure circuits of extraction can be found in Chile. Arboleda (2020) has shown in a landmark study that northern Chile's copper mining territories are enmeshed in transnational extractive, infrastructure, and financial networks of the planetary mine, which has devastating impacts on the local level in terms of social, political, and environmental issues. An example of corporate participation in this field is the Luksic group, one of Chile's most powerful conglomerates. As a result of its diversification and global expansion in recent years, it controls companies in a wide range of industries, including mining, finance, banking, telecommunications, and transportation (Leiva 2021). The group extends geographically and extracts (infrastructure-mediated) rent from territories all over Chile and beyond. Its origin and one of its main centers of operation remains Antofagasta, one of the centers of Chile's copper industry.

With Antofagasta as the bottleneck, Luksic operates an integrated logistics and production chain that includes extraction, transportation, loading and shipping activities, and extends from the heights of the Andean mountains to the Atacama Desert, through Antofagasta's urban fabric and the Pacific Ocean to those ports in North America and China where minerals are released (Lukas, 2022). Over 3000 meters above sea level, Luksic begins its logistic chain 180 kilometers from Antofagasta, where the group operates the copper and gold mines Zentínela and Zaldivar through Antofagasta Minerals, the largest private mining company of Chilean origin. From Zentínela and Zaldivar, minerals are transported through pipelines, highways, and Ferrocarril Antofagasta Bolivia (FCAB) to the Antofagasta port facilities after extraction. FCAB, founded in 1888 during the nitrate epoch and owned by the Luksic Group (through Antofagasta plc) since 1980, operates a rail network of over 900 kilometers that is exclusively dedicated to transporting mining inputs and products, such as sulfuric acid and copper cathodes. A major destination for the minerals is the ATI-port, controlled by Luksic, which also caters exclusively to the mining industry. The minerals are first stored at ATI and then loaded onto large container ships, mainly those owned by the Compañía Sudamericana de Vapores (CSAV). In addition

to taking control of CSAV in 2011, in 2014 Luksic acquired the German shipping company Hapag-Lloyd and has a fleet of 200 ships and is the fourth largest container shipping company in the world. Between 2003 and 2015 Luksic also controlled Aguas Antofagasta, the principal water company of the city.

What becomes clear in this description of a vertically integrated logistic chain for rent extraction is that the big private corporations deserve more attention in the study of territorial accumulation in Latin America. They operationalize and strategically connect rural and urban spaces through all sorts of material and socio-political infrastructures and are some of the key players of infrastructure-led development.

6.4. Case Study (II): Commoning Platforms in Ecuador and Brazil

Based on the study of infrastructural practices in Monte Sinaí, Guayaquil, Ecuador, Leandro Minuchin advances the notion of “popular infrastructures.” These “illustrate the workings and traces of urban subjectivities and give consistency to local organizations that demand a voice and presence in the urban future of Monte Sinaí” (Minuchin, 2021, p. 8). As infra-commoning, popular infrastructures crystallise socio-political relations, yet while popular infrastructures sustain alternative socio-spatial configurations, they also materialise the overlapping and competing urbanisation agendas that characterise settlement management in Latin America. In Monte Sinaí, popular infrastructures emerge as delayed, incomplete housing projects but also as the incremental interventions that reveal the numerous actors (committees, private developers, NGOs, local representatives) and the constantly adapted regulatory layers that prefigure urbanisation in peripheral settlements. These infrastructures are mediums that organise politics, projecting on to the landscape not a planned but a prefigured urbanisation and other models of territorial organisation, including the “counter-models” to government and private agendas (Minuchin, 2021, p. 9).

Tracing the developments of three land occupations in Belo Horizonte, Brazil, namely, Dandara, Eliana Silva and Rosa Leão, Amin (2014, p. 148) defines infra-commoning as Eliana Silva, the locality where infra-commoning seems to be stronger, features a number of communal infrastructural projects whose “very aesthetic and functionality [...] help to maintain [a] collective ethos”. This is called infra-commoning (ibid.)

6.5. Concluding Thoughts

The literature and examples reviewed in this section indicate that infrastructure is a contested policy field that may serve different economic, social and environmental aims. Whilst the desire for global market integration and extractive motive are clear in how roadways are being extended through multiple Latin American geographies, the region has also witnessed the rise of new logics and practices for the development and management of infrastructure. The challenge ahead for critical policy analysis in the context of contested territorial accumulation is to tease out both the discursive and material benefits that each infrastructural project brings about for its various proponents and challengers whilst also mobilising comparative and relational techniques of analysis to understand the broader regimes of infrastructure investment that condition the possibilities for territorial development.

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7. A PROPOSAL FOR A REGENERATIVE ACTION FOR THE COLLISIVE SITES OF THE SECOND MODERNITY METROPOLITAN REGION

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7.1 Introduction

The field of research is in Pianura Padana Region in Northern Italy, where the cultural logic of agriculture persists and manifests itself as a type of heritage even if the logistics sector is occupying the fertile land pervasively. The research deals with the physical dimension of the metropolis, which the EU Community identified as the twin transitions (green and digital) field of action.

Considering the challenges of the growing socioeconomic inequalities due to the metropolitanization of our territories, we are dealing with Harvey's (2004) accumulation by dispossession.

We verify Metropolitan Cartography's methodology as a tool that allows us to enlighten the values of the metropolitan collusive site (Corner, 2006) as contested territories and see how metropolitan dynamics' transformations on the space-time map can be combined with the interstitial world of local communities.

The issue of poor coordination between transport and land use planning must be explored at a local level and whether it is a problem at a central level and, therefore, at the level of the European Union.

Thinking about logistics, in theory, means looking at supply chain techniques. There is, therefore, a macroscopic level of metropolitan planning that needs to be understood. According to a definition typical of the discipline of transport, it is necessary to have a territory that, case by case, is organised according to the structure of the distribution networks serving that territory. Theoretically, what is essential to observe are the strategic positions where the facilities of the distribution networks are and, therefore, where warehouses and distribution centres serving metropolitan areas are located. In the case of Milan, for example, today, warehouses are almost at the city's gates.

Moreover, in the intermediate areas between logistics and the urban fabric, entire areas often need help finding an opportunity for conversion to new uses. These are typical cases of collusive sites. On the other hand, a large amount of land is urbanised and intended for parking lots and areas dedicated to loading/unloading and storage. In many cases, these areas are used only for a few hours of the day, while for the remaining time, they remain deserted. These areas are completely devoid of common and public spaces, often protected by gates and walls that do not allow any exchange with the city. Still, that produces degradation at their borders, also generating in the citizens a sense of insecurity and hostility towards this metropolis' productive function, highly polluting, not resolved by the promise of new employment possibilities threatened by the increasingly intensive use of the automation of the logistics activities in the future.

Moreover, the Covid-19 pandemic is a catalyst to reflect on public space' structures, organisations and habits. It provides an opportunity to create sustainable and positive change in our cities with an impact that will be felt well beyond the crisis. The project's research question is how to maintain the quality of life in metropolitan areas and address climate change and eco-

problems by implementing precisely in these interface and interphase areas where the impact on citizens due to metropolitan infrastructural projects is most perceptible. It aims to produce a pattern model and the practices it allows to interconnect the two rural and urban fabrics generating a new urban-industrial-rural ecosystem. At the same time, the location of production units can be the basis for social innovation policies integrated with district regeneration policies (Gouverneur, 2014).

The local space design project, first, must introduce the metropolitan urbanity perspective, arguing about the role of sustainable mobility in constructing the metropolitan city culture. Through mapping projects, metropolitan architecture's task is to build a new pattern's form of metropolitan urbanity and strengthen a feeling of adequacy (Lynch, 1960) between places and inhabitants. The research question is how local people can tune in to the 'other values' brought by globalisation.

We start from an assumption of vision that does not go back to a restructuring or reconstruction of an idyllic landscape, an inhabited and environmentally sustainable post-sharecropping countryside, which we have lost. Suppose we are going to redesign the fringe areas of the metropolitan city. It is necessary to integrate the two chronologies, the urban and the rural; then, the countryside timing that a citizen will never have, becomes crucial because there is a need to bring both visions together.

It is a matter of redesigning and reclaiming back to the metropolitan city the collusive sites for regenerative agriculture and new local markets. It is a proposal for a regenerative agriculture model for the green transition that benefits from the localised analysis and networking capabilities between communities and markets offered by the digital transition and sustainable mobility. Cultivating in the city or farming in the countryside must provide the same welfare choice, even concerning the market's possibilities. Implementing both territories and their landscapes, if we put urban visions in the countryside and the opposite of the country in the city functions areas, it is possible to regenerate our environments without conflicting with sectoral visions by integrating the two twin transitions, green and digital.

7.2 The practice of Metropolitan Discipline

A syntactic transformation is taking place in the city today. Cosmopolitan globalisation, or new colonialism, disables sites, so those past urban individualities are not reinterpreted according to their position but read on a different scale. In the Practice of Metropolitan Discipline field of actions (Contin, Giordano, and Nacke, 2021), we are struggling for a possible alternative model of development of the territory, the region and the metropolitan cities of "colonial" and non-colonial countries, which can qualify democracy as a concept of generalised, participatory and relational power shared on an equal footing, built by a plurality of actors (Cavarero, 2019) having the defence of the environment and intelligence of its territories as a shared project (Contin, Galiulo, 2022).

Our Metropolitan Approach to Complexity deals with the metropolitan city read and understood as a field of forces inhabited by "agents" who freely interact with other subjects across their mutual boundaries, thus meaning "border" as the fundamental physical and disciplinary "field of action". The fragile territory we deal with is linked to a complex metropolitan dimension. It is an incredible laboratory of infinite potential, a field of positive and negative forces. The Metropolitan Approach to Complexity comprises three phases that give the metropolitan issues their specific general context from which to start with the analysis of metropolitan complexity; identification of local values and intelligence for sustainable urban development at the metropolitan scale; and design of a robust image of the public and common civic space of the interface and interphase spaces.

The fragile territories of globalisation are cases in which economic, social, political, or cultural connections at the global level converge. It means that our territories are crossed by global logic, which should keep us from losing sight of territorial crossings at the local, metropolitan

and regional levels. In short, the logistics area's collusive sites are territories of globalisation, implying that they are bearers of synthesis instances to understand the global dynamics and spaces of intervention of multi-scale agents interacting with local narratives.

Dealing with metropolitan collusive sites dimension requires working in different contexts, such as compact cities, agricultural areas, watersheds, and interface-interphase areas "in-between" diverse landscapes. The primary needs are understanding the complexity of the metropolis, recognising the gaps between theory and practice, and providing the proper tools to address these gaps.

We address two components, an ethical definition of twin transitions (green and digital) and the inequalities and inequities they produce. Western countries continue to create them by moving to the countries of the Global South, where they go back to growing intensively, generating further inequalities that lead people to migrate.

We emphasise the metropolitan systemic value. Technology, the digital infrastructure transition that Europe is interested in, can make people cultivate smarter and can help to bring the inhabitant back to the countryside if we politically determine welfare that allows equal opportunities between the city and the country. That is our proposal vision for a sustainable green transition.

In a way, we are saying that digital infrastructure brings welfare, that is, a sense of 'adequacy' to a place, even if it is not located in the city's centre, because it determines a connection.

In this sense, digital social infrastructure can be said to enhance a different lifestyle. The systemic and integrated metropolitan dimension of places, which therefore sees the elimination of the classical dichotomies between city and country and nature and culture, is the scope of our proposal.

Generally, collusive sites (Corner, 2006) are determined in carrying out a metropolitan infrastructural operation because the infrastructure determines the location of settlement to the detriment of what was there before. It was nature or agriculture which are, to a certain extent, removed and depressed while they need to be integrated to an undeniable degree. It is necessary to study the impact of the infrastructure in constituting collusive sites vis-à-vis the pre-existing buildings and spaces that become disused and neglected.

Nevertheless, social issues of inequality and iniquity must be integrated into the discourse of collusive sites.

Therefore, through twin transitions, new techniques and infrastructures must be developed for logistics – sustainable mobility, first – and agriculture through more sustainable production practices.

From this point of view, the logistics example can be specified precisely concerning the fact that the logistics compounds are created on roads upgraded and thus clogged and expanded, following a pure incrementalism principle. The result is that not only do they make agriculture they occupy become neglected, but they also make all urban structures that interfere with logistics function become neglected by degrading them. Moreover, physical fact determines people's inequality.

7.3 The relevance of the metropolitan discipline area for theorising territorial accumulation and contested territories. New community forms and urban-rural practices

Knowing and understanding inequality and subalternity in the ecological and digital transition is necessary. There are four dimensions of inequality that we consider historically.

The first dimension is class inequality, which has been an essential aspect of human life and has been set aside in the thinking of the last thirty years but remains fundamental. In the history of the modern age, awareness of this division led to movements, battles, and conflicts. Through this conflict, there was an increase in the power of labour and thus liberation from basic needs.

Work gained control, and people could devote themselves to other dimensions of human life, recognising the differences that the traditional way of life had hitherto concealed.

The second is gender inequality. It stems from the patriarchal drift, i.e., the attribution to men, which is sexism, of specific roles, functions, aspirations and powers in society that does not recognise women.

The third dimension is the one that has dominated another part of the history of capitalism in the West and which also led to a phase of slavery, namely the idea of thinking that there are different roles and different human types linked to race. Let us use the word race to ethnicity, as Angela Devis used it. That is a form of ex-ante discrimination that produces inequality.

The fourth dimension of inequality is the awareness of our unbalanced relationship with the ecosystem.

Of these four dimensions, subalternity is the common characteristic. The subalternity of labour vis-à-vis those who also own capital, of women vis-à-vis men, of all races vis-à-vis the Caucasian race, which is considered central to the entire ecosystem of human beings, of the earth, animals and plants vis-à-vis human beings. Tackling these four subalternities together is the cornerstone of a new form of emancipation that must start with conceptualisations but be done very concretely.

Our proposal aims to reduce the subalternities linked to the four inequalities as a mission through recommendations that offer a solution by thinking about how metropolitan language can enable a metropolitan culture and structured, systemic thinking about its inter-scalar co-construction.

In addressing the issue of the regeneration of metropolitan collusive sites from their green-grey structure, we intend to address the issue of inequality concerning the four dimensions we have identified for two of the sectors proposed by the European transition project : Industrial processes and product use and agriculture, forestry and other land use.

It is not a question of returning to the agricultural civilisation; everything that comes from digital and new technology can be used for a different kind of metropolis that is understood as a territory that dialogues with and includes the countryside.

The European community is asking us to help decision-makers make decisions because twin transitions may produce inequality, and we will also add inequity. We do not start our analysis from social inequality but the neglected reality of our metropolitan collusive sites. Speaking of a metropolis, the dimension of the society should be complemented by anthropological vision as well as archaeology and not only history.

The important metropolitan starting point is that complexity of scale must be looked at from the perspective of the new metropolitan structure that transcends administrative boundaries.

It is precisely the metropolitanisation of our places and territories that de-specialises and de-territorialises, and therefore, when we lower the quality of our territories because we interfere them with infrastructures and a series of necessary metropolitan functions (see logistics), this produces a lowering of the quality of life of the people who live there. That happens especially in places that James Corner has called collusive sites.

Collusive sites are places for Corner, an ecologist, where ecotones conflict. For an architect, it is more interesting to talk about different landscape shades. So, we must determine metropolitan transformation projects that can process different shades of lifestyle quality. This is important because usually, those who make decisions about the territory and who do so through an algorithm instead start from program requirements. At the same time, at the metropolitan scale, it is more important to understand what the range of qualities of these territories is and which cannot be lost: the local variants that must become metropolitan invariants.

A homoeopathic operation comes to mind: we should start with regenerative recombination of the constituent elements before inserting something external.

Collisive sites are the places where the interfaces between city and country, country and infrastructure, country and industry, city and industry, city and nature are also interfaces - spatial and temporal dimensions - are landscapes that are usually neglected and within which there is also a time problem. The time problem is the real problem rather than the social and the space problems because the second-generation metropolitan transformation is immeasurable and happens quickly.

Healthy land has always been capable of absorbing transformation, but the short time of change is a variable we have never experienced. Therefore, these collision sites can remain stationary for years and centuries or transform very quickly, incapable of adaptation or sustainable transformation.

Moreover, they are often inhabited by different populations not tied to that place; they carry other knowledge (pluriverse) and must adapt to new customs. Introducing them to a new, different way of using natural resources is essential.

Following Magnaghi's thinking (Magnaghi, 2008, p.7.), globalisation has progressively deprived us of the foundational elements of the city over time. De-differentiation, de-corporealisation, de-memorisation, de-complexification, and de-contextualisation are all deprivations that have led to the forgetting of the knowledge and skills of building a differentiated, contextualised and articulated environment on the human scale as F. Choay (1996) reminded us. This loss weakens us because this knowledge can establish a possible dialogue of foundation and re-foundation between successive civilisations and the soul of places.

For Choay, there is no building without dialogue with those for whom one builds. And this happens in an inter-scalar perspective and in the production of rules to be applied concerning each natural and cultural context, not models to be reproduced or imitated.

We are talking about the need for a "statute of the territory and its places" (Magnaghi 2008, 13) capable of indicating good construction practices, transformation at different scales, and the use of new technologies that respect and feed off the rules of long-term reproduction of the place.

In the age of globalisation, 'uni-versal' rules of good building and good governance need to be produced alongside 'pluri-versal', i.e., place-specific rules.

In the construction of a metropolitan narrative based on the definition of metropolitan agro-urban territories as a choice of life, it is necessary to rethink the role of agriculture, the relationship between city and country that is nowadays declined in the collisive sites - inside and outside the urban fabric - and an economic, infrastructural landscape that has as its vision, not the agro-business and logistics logics of extensive peri-urban agriculture, but an alternative and regenerative idea of the now impoverished soils, that can give voice to what is considered marginal, small and of quality. In this context, consider the introduction of twin transitions that can overcome the differences between places and people.

Suppose we want to ensure that the city and the suburbs are not losers because the agricultural extractivism comprised of hectares of monoculture has destroyed the idea of landscape reproduction. In that case, we must get out of the logic of extensive industrial agriculture. We have to redesign the interphase locations by thinking of a small farm of 5 hectares, two hectares in irregular shapes that do not have these needs.

To avoid creating inequality through IT infrastructure, we need a system capable of producing an exciting and new management method, i.e., how to put the consumer in touch with those who produce quality and are close by. We would not only make the system more efficient but would still require the training of personnel who know both the production and the commercial sectors and therefore have training in both fields.

7.3. Research programme and comparative strategy between Europe and Latin America. The Atlas of CT

The relationship between space, memory, and representation in the digital age has experienced a substantial increase. Therefore, the topography for exploring the city requires the development of methods, tools, and experiments to record the metropolitan territory. For this reason, we use the most recent mapping technologies in Metropolitan Cartography (MC) research. Metropolitan Cartography, however, has accomplished that fundamental operation of an analytic in which every element, every point on the map, has a pre-existing value that is valued in both the green and grey, both the natural green and the man-made green. That allows us to control its transformation to conserve and preserve the vitality of nature's self-reproduction that must still be made possible and, above all, be able to be observed and enjoyed in the landscape.

Twin transitions, green and digital, then, are the technologies of human processing of everything related to green-grey infrastructure that must be carefully explored in the project, avoiding the inequalities they can produce on the contrary.

We are planning to compare the world's metropolitan cities to produce maps able to spatialise the impact of metropolitan infrastructures and city growth on the territories. An Atlas can be fundamental to categorise the possible cases of sensitivity, exposure, and reaction capability due to the metropolitan infrastructure projects. A new tool is necessary to decide on a possible metropolitan architecture project.

We expect the readers of the Atlas will better understand the complexity of managing cities and their territories, identify successful practices that could be transferred to other areas, and introduce the debate about the need for a new planning vision accounting shared approaches related to the multiple scales' integration.

Atlas is conceived as a Platform that allows the creation of a knowledge web-based community, instrumental to the foundation of the new Contested Territories issues awareness. It is an IT platform that manages and publishes spatial data in interactive interpretive maps. The platform will host data of different natures in GIS format geo-referenced, which may then be categorised through specific keywords of territorial analysis to facilitate access to the materials available for the various metropolitan areas.

It could be one of the fundamentals of the Contested Training Program. The Glossary is necessary because the Contested Territories' knowledge is based on different definitions and concepts. It must be analysed through a multidisciplinary approach, which includes various fields using specific terminologies within each node/team. There is a limit to using existing terms without adjustments because they were used within the conventional framework of the existing phenomena in a specific field. It is mandatory to have a common language that helps communication to be clear and compelling, considering the complexity and the importance of collaboration among the experts. A Glossary provides a list of keywords fundamental in discussing metropolitan issues. Some terms are borrowed from a field and shared, whereas others will be redefined in the following context of metropolitan scale. Redefining and creating words as a common base of the discipline is the first step in creating a comprehensive conceptualisation and new knowledge of the new domain. The Contested Glossary is not a simple list of words with static definitions. The complexity of the approach requires a different perspective in framing the issues and solutions. The Glossary is a way to begin creating the new conceptual structure of the Contested Territories knowledge. It is an open-ended collection of vocabulary from various fields and discussed by experts.

Moreover, considering the concepts of similar words in different cultures using different languages, it is essential to be inclusive in comparing different contexts in Latin America and Europe.

A descriptive text will accompany the Glossary. The text records the evolution of the keywords and related concepts as the team develops throughout the project. It is shared online, allowing people to search and contribute further to developing awareness of the Glossary and Contested Territories.

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8. THE PLACE OF POPULAR HABITAT IN THE PRODUCTION OF BLUE AND GREEN INFRASTRUCTURE: CASE STUDIES IN THE PERIPHERY OF THE METROPOLITAN REGION OF BUENOS AIRES

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8.1. Presentation

This section addresses the dynamics and socio-territorial tensions inherent in the production processes of urban infrastructures and the management of popular habitat. The analysis is based on the comparative study of three self-management experiences located in the southern sector of the Metropolitan Region of Buenos Aires. (RMBA). In particular, it is interesting to analyze the processes of co-production of knowledge between local communities, grassroots organizations and public universities, aimed at socio-environmental intervention in areas of high vulnerability and urban precariousness. The approach of the case studies allows us to recover the debates on the environment as a transversal dimension to all public policies. At the same time, the notions of gray, blue and green infrastructures are taken, highlighting the differences in terms of the format of design and execution of policies, the place reserved for citizen participation and the way of managing environmental variables.

8.2. Background discussions

The provision of infrastructure and the public policies associated with that production of space represent an area of debate, in which not only contributions on infrastructure policies emerge, but also on the needs of social reproduction, daily life and the change from demands to practices (Sitrin, 2014). Both popular infrastructures (Minuchin, 2021) and popular logistics (Minuchin and Maino, 2022), appear deeply rooted in the functioning of local organizations and their struggles to ensure the acquisition of goods and services that facilitate the reproduction and improvement of vulnerable and marginalized communities. By producing public infrastructures based on solidarity structures, these interventions appear as concrete material oppositions to territorial accumulation (Horn et al., 2021).

In this way, policies “from above”, expressed through traditional plans, programs and projects, are beginning to be challenged “from below” by popular initiatives oriented towards the reproduction of life. These are perspectives that imply new logics, condensed in the idea of “distributive systems”, based on decentralized elements that connect with broader networks and that operate in opposition to hierarchical systems from the top down (Escobar, 2019). These questions are posed by cases in which there is a certain articulation of initiatives in both directions, as hybrid forms of infrastructure co-production. Added to this tension is another one that originates from views on gray and green/blue infrastructures, so there is a double process of socio-technical assemblage: on forms of production and on the environmental dimension. New urban transformations are required combining imagination and existing materials through “design strategies capable of creating new infrastructures for life” (Escobar, 2019:40).

The debate must be situated, considering the particularities of the context of peripheral urbanization in Latin America, characterized by precarious conditions in infrastructure, services and housing, but within the framework of heterogeneous landscapes (Caldeira, 2017) into which in

tension with other urban production processes. This same author points out that residents are the main agents of space production, but the State is present in various ways, often late and after these spaces have been produced and inhabited (Caldeira, 2017).

Amin (2014) refers to an infrastructure seen as “hybrids of human and non-human associations”, conceptualized as a “sociotechnical assemblage” (corporate interests, regulatory standards, social expectations, human-software-hardware-intelligence hybrids, historical legacies of organization and provision of services). Based on his analysis of cases of occupations in Brazil, he highlights the design, existence and culture of “the common”, compared to classic cases of interventions in consolidated favelas, where design from above prevails, without popular participation, with the provision over the years, partial and conditional access, of low quality and with urban consolidation with risk of displacement.

Kozak et al. (2021) state that blue and green infrastructures (BGI) refer to the recognition of the innate capacities of green space and the ecosystems in which they are immersed, to produce environmental benefits and quality of life. In the specific case of water management policies, the blue and green line is presented in opposition to the historical and conventional management of water surpluses, with emphasis on gray infrastructure (conventional rainwater, generally underground and impermeable), where the BGI “ responds both to a demand to improve the environmental quality of cities and to respond to the limitations of traditional solutions, by taking advantage of the geomorphic features of natural systems” (Kozak et al ., 2021:12).

According to these authors, the BGI would represent a model suitable for micro interventions and to be gradually scaled up to combined micro and macro projects, highlighting that the BGI and its maintenance require simple technologies and local development, having a greater incidence on the demand for local labor (Kozak et al ., 2021).

However, the debates on green and blue infrastructures also require reflection on the different levels of popular participation in the management of public resources. As in the debates around the self-management of housing (Pelli, 2001; Rodríguez, 2020), the production of infrastructures and interventions on the popular habitat at the hands of community organizations can be analyzed as a differentiated gradient according to the level of access to these resources, which may be “spontaneous”, “assisted” or “co-managed”, public-community processes.

8.3. The case studies

The selected cases are located in the municipalities of Alte. Brown, Esteban Echeverría and Quilmes, in the South zone of the RMBA. These cases refer to processes of self-management of the popular habitat and environmental variables, based on knowledge co-production approaches between local communities, grassroots organizations and public universities. In all cases, the background of territories characterized by popular urbanization, of villas and informal settlements, with marked environmental problems, such as water pollution, floods or management of urban solid waste, is shared.

8.3.1. Case 1: Redefinition of environmental liabilities as an opportunity to improve the popular habitat

The first case takes place in the La Victoria, Las Chacritas and El Triunfo neighborhoods, within the municipality of Esteban Echeverría. These are informal settlements formed in an area characterized by the presence of old properties with brick cellars, which are the subject of a strong real estate outpost for the construction of gated communities (Apaolaza and Venturini, 2021). These brick cellars, most of which are subject to flooding, have historically been seen as urban-environmental liabilities, on which it is necessary to generate targeted remediation policies. In this scenario, the possibility of converting these properties into closed neighborhoods such as countries or marinas is interpreted as a reasonable urban-environmental option. This has led to the favoring of permissive changes in land use regulations in various

municipalities (HCD Pdte. Perón, 2016; Esteban Echeverría, 2019; HCD Alte. Brown, 2020), often contrary to the recommendations developed by experts. in the matter (Garay, 2012). The emergence of the cumulative impacts of the successive floods and water diversions end up contributing to aggravate the flood events associated with the local stream basin (La Lucía, Ortega, Medrano streams, etc.). Faced with this model of privatizing reconversion, the initiative arose to think of these cellars as "new wetlands", that is, portions of the territory that, despite their significant soil degradation, "fulfill a valuable ecological and social function, since they preserve islands of biodiversity (birds, lutrinos and amphibians mainly), protect strategic aquifer recharge areas of the headwaters and middle basins of local streams, and help to mitigate floods" (Apaolaza and Venturini, 2021:6). In this case, it is interesting to review some incipient experiences carried out by neighborhood organizations in association with chairs of the Geography career of the University of Buenos Aires (UBA), which, based on social cartography workshops and popular surveys, precisely seek to reinterpret these liabilities as urban-environmental opportunities, based on popular habitat management practices.

8.3.2. Case 2: Popular management of urban watersheds and flood risk prevention

The second case takes place in the neighborhoods located on the banks of the Las Piedras and San Francisco streams, in the municipalities of Alte. Brown and Quilmes, and involves the articulation between social and community organizations, and professional teams from the Faculty of Exact and Natural Sciences of the UBA, the National Technological University (UTN) and the National Water Institute (INA), with the support of the Japan Science and Technology Agency (JST) and the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA). This case is made up of two specific, though related, experiences. On the one hand, there is a project (in progress) for the community construction of a public park on recovered land (former garbage dumps), located on the banks of the San Francisco stream, where sports, recreational, education and environmental protection activities are carried out. These are 13.6 green hectares that constitute an area of great environmental value for the ecosystem, since they not only add green spaces to a vulnerable urban area, but also contribute to the absorption of excess rainwater, preventing the stream overflows and generates flooding in the surrounding neighborhoods. In turn, carrying out sports and recreational activities in these properties allows access to a public park with unique characteristics in the locality, integrating a body of water that has historically been seen as a problem, as part of the urban landscape, revaluing its existence as a fundamental socio-environmental element (Graziano et al., 2019; Graziano, 2021), following the line of green and blue infrastructures. On the other hand, this case has a second experience, represented by a flood early warning project. It was made from the installation of a network of pluviometric and fluvial gauging stations, with which the data collected over ten years were modeled, to establish correlated patterns between rainfall and behavior of water bodies, in terms of the timing of floods. This monitoring and prediction system works in flood risk situations as a popular early warning mechanism, capable of notifying dozens of community organizations located throughout the basin.

8.3.3. Case 3: Co-management of public funds in the urban and environmental design of the popular habitat

The last case takes place in the 14 de Febrero, Las Lilas and Los Altos neighborhoods, within the municipality of Almirante Brown, and is represented by a set of popular design projects for infrastructures and green and recreational spaces. It is an experience promoted by community organizations, accompanied by the advice of professionals from the Faculty of Architecture of the UBA, in which a set of actions for the design and construction of a comprehensive green space is proposed, which includes community equipment, tree planting and provision of sports infrastructures, all framed within a perspective of environmental sustainability and direct community participation. The most interesting thing is that, unlike the previous cases, this project has state financing, through a line called "Early Works Projects" (POTs). This is one of the forms of intervention developed by the Secretary of Socio-Urban Integration, which allows the

allocation of resources directly to community organizations and cooperatives, in order to intervene on the deficient infrastructure and housing conditions of popular neighborhoods. Although it is an embryonic experience, it presents the potential to explore mixed public-community operation, when co-managing resources for neighborhood improvement.

8.4. Preliminary questions

Some questions are proposed below that will guide the development of the cases and, in turn, can contribute to consolidating a comparative strategy with other studies that are carried out within the framework of Contested Territories.

What is the relationship between public infrastructure policies and popular intervention initiatives in the habitat? What articulations and conflicts are registered? How are the various infrastructure production processes linked to the accumulation processes linked to public works?

What are the devices implemented in both types of initiative in relation to the design, construction, appropriation of urban infrastructure and popular habitat?

How is the environmental dimension incorporated into the imagination/production of infrastructure? To what extent do the green and blue infrastructure proposals contribute to the generation of improvements in the daily life of the communities? What particulars do these proposals have regarding collective construction?

How are environmental liabilities visualized in territorial accumulation processes? What examples of cases and situations reflect a view of these environmental liabilities as a potential improvement in the conditions of social reproduction and daily life? What examples of cases and situations reflect a view of these environmental liabilities as a potential source for new modalities of territorial accumulation?

To what extent does self-managed infrastructure become "identity" for popular neighborhoods?

What scalar tensions are generated in the production of urban infrastructure and the management of popular habitat? How is the articulation of the infrastructure produced in micro interventions built with larger scale networks controlled and managed by other actors?

What particularities do these processes acquire in the Latin American peripheries? What processes of territorial accumulation dispute access to land and the production of urbanization in these peripheries?

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9. “GREEN” URBAN POLICIES AND TERRITORIAL ACCUMULATION IN THE METROPOLITAN AREA OF BUENOS AIRES, ARGENTINA

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9.1. Introduction

This contribution reflects on the use of “the environment” in urban policies as a mechanism of territorial accumulation. The analysis focuses on the metropolitan region of Buenos Aires, Argentina over the past twenty years. For this, we attend to three different processes: the implementation of urban ventures on coastal spaces: riverside, flood-prone or wetland areas, where their proximity to road infrastructures is used to obtain extraordinary income (Abba, 2010; Wertheimer, 2019, 2020); the appropriations of urban spaces with agricultural experiences (Gallardo Araya 2015, 2017); and the execution of the Sanitation Plan for the Matanza-Riachuelo Basin (Carman 2017; Olejarczyk 2021).

The above are experiences from ethnographies (two recently completed, one in progress) developed in the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires, in the municipality of Vicente López and in that of Almirante Brown (Gallardo Araya, 2021; Wertheimer, 2019 and 2020), administrative units that, as a whole, make up what is called the Metropolitan Area of Buenos Aires (hereinafter, AMBA). Based on these cases, we wonder how urban policies based on environmental arguments can favor, delay or even reverse mechanisms of territorial accumulation.

With this purpose, first of all, we develop the main aspects of the anthropological and ethnographic perspective on urban-environmental public policies (Roseberry, 2002; Das and Poole, 2008; Asad, 2008; Shore, 2010). Secondly, we review academic debates that problematize the advance of “the environment” in multiple social fields of meaning and practice (Leite Lopes, 2004; Azuela, 2006). Finally, we seek to put these works in dialogue with the mechanisms of territorial accumulation, which “is inextricably linked to a general crisis of capitalism in its broadest sense (cultural, political and economic)” (WP Territorial Accumulation, 2022).

9.2. The ethnographic approach to urban-environmental policies

The anthropological perspective for the analysis of public policies seeks to recover its intrinsic ambiguity and polysemy. Following Shore (2010), the aspects that make up a policy must be understood in the unique historical, political and socioeconomic context in which they are produced; with which it is highly relevant to identify the complex network of actors and institutions involved. They elaborate different interpretations of what politics is and what it should do, pro-

ducing “conflicting definitions” (Shore, 2010: 24). In this sense, any policy will present unforeseen and unexpected consequences, since its development and scope escape any pretense of measurement and control.

Likewise, another very significant aspect for this type of approach is that public policies incorporate the classification systems involved in their formulation, while providing feedback on said systems. The classification systems produced by the State are linked, for Roseberry (2002), with the fact that “the State never stops talking” (Corrigan and Sayer, 1985 in Roseberry, 2002: 9). In an act of permanent enunciation, the State accepts certain activities and statements while discarding others. In turn, the protest repertoires adopt these official languages in order to be heard. Thus, “common discursive frameworks” are established, which are stressed, disputed and, on occasions, managed to break.

However, as Das and Poole (2008: 22) point out, the capacity for action in subjects that interact with the State is not reduced to acts of resistance, but rather its conceptual limits are extended and reestablished in everyday interactions as such subjects struggle for their survival or the search for justice. The authors propose an anthropological analysis focused on the notion of margins understood as “sites that are not outside the State but, like rivers, cross its entire body”, in which practices that simultaneously combine “an outside and inside the law”; “places where the State is continuously constituted in the recesses of daily life” (ibid., 15, 17 and 27). In this line, Asad (2008: 61) points out that the State is not a static object but an abstract structure and that “in its totality it is a margin”.

The last aspect to point out is linked to the moral effects of public policies. As Shore (2010) points out, all public policy produces subjectivities and political subjects. Certainly, in the process of its implementation, identities are not only assigned to the populations involved, but these identities are actively produced from the interactions between the actors involved. In this production of identities, a moral production is also put into play that involves certain “ranges of humanity” (Butler, 2006; Carman, 2017), as well as mechanisms of humanization and dehumanization (Fassin, 2016) that reproduce logics of precariousness, and that can amplify the violence involved in these processes.

9.3. The environmentalization of the social

In the cases analyzed, we observed, a process of greening the urban and housing policies involved, a process that is part of the general trend of what various authors call the greening of the social (Balbi, 2007; Carman, 2011; Leite Lopes, 2006) that refers to the discursive and practical game in which the topics of environmentalism are strategically put into play by different actors involved in the course of conflictive social processes, since those topics are part of a valid language imbued with legitimacy in the local and international public agendas. In this context, different mobilized actors incorporate the environmental issue as part of their repertoire of interests and claims, while private individuals, the business sector and the political sphere also make strategic use of the environment. Thus, environmental topics can be translated and integrated into rival political projects, coming to be combined in situations as dissimilar as struggles for emancipation and equity in access to natural resources as well as in pro-market practices.

Environmentalism harbors several currents of thought and action, for which it is more appropriate to refer to “multiple environmentalisms” (Bebbington and Bebbington, 2009; Gudynas, 1992; Martínez Alier, 2009). From the multiplicity of typologies proposed by various authors, we will focus on the environmental currents predominantly present in the analyzed case studies, green marketing and eco-efficiency, elaborated from various contributions (Acselrad, Campello do A. Mello and das Neves Bezerra, 2009; Foladori, 2005; Gudynas, 1992; Harvey, 1996; Martínez Alier, 2009; O'Connor, 1994; Wagner, 2010).

(a) Green Marketing

It is a set of discourses and practices that consider that environmental concerns should not interfere in the path towards capital accumulation, for which environmental care is subordinated to continuous economic growth and capital accumulation (Harvey, 1996). Concerns for the environment are only taken into account if they can be added as consumption preferences to be satisfied, in a scheme that does not question the accumulation of capital, efficiency and economic growth.

Green marketing practices they focus on adapting nature consistently with profitability and capital accumulation. In order to build an environmentally responsible image, green marketing it has been disinterested in the scientific evidence of “environmentally friendly” practices and is concerned merely with presenting a credible “green” image to consumers (O'Connor, 1994).

(b) Eco-efficiency

Unlike green marketing, the sector identified as "eco-efficient" considers that environmental care is necessary and that it can be compatible with the goals of economic growth (Acselrad et al., 2009; Gudynas, 1992; Harvey, 1996). The “eco-efficiency” It is a current within environmentalism that starts from the premise that, although industrial activity causes environmental damage, with effective controls it is possible to coexist with economic growth and care for the planet and its preservation for future generations. Many companies found in environmentalism a stimulus to adopt superior, less polluting technologies –certified by scientific studies– that simultaneously generate greater efficiency in production and, as a result, make environmentally friendly products available, forming a growing segment from within the market.

This conception of economic development and environmental care constitutes the dominant ecological thought in political, business and multilateral agencies, since it does not question the growth model, but rather naturalizes their assumptions regarding what is produced, how it is produced and for what purpose and whose benefit it is produced The concentration of development benefits in the hands of a few people, as well as the disproportionate allocation of environmental risks to the poorest remain absent from the discussion.

In the works that have been developed within Contested Territories, at least three categories are recognized that explain the geographies of capital accumulation: a) accumulation by appropriation of unpaid work, b) accumulation by dispossession as an internal element, and external of the capitalist system; c) and accumulation in the fabric of life (WP Territorial Accumulation, 2022). The environmental currents mentioned here are related to this last axis, which develops extractivism (Gudynas, 2015, 2017) or neo-extractivism (Svampa, 2019; Gago and Mezzadra, 2015) and the theory focused on the ecological (Moore, 2020). More specifically our line of work aims to understand urban-environmental policies under the framework of an "extractive matrix" nourishing ourselves with various contributions (Gudynas, 2012; Seoane, Taddei and Algranati, 2013; Svampa, Sola Alvarez and Bottaro, 2009; Svampa, 2017). Likewise, we deepen the ideas associated with the “environmental turn” using political ecology as a perspective (O'Connor, 1988; Foster, 2000 and Smith, 1996).

9.4. “Green” urban policies and territorial accumulation

In this section we seek to account for the relevance that environmental issues have acquired in urban policies based on three case studies located in the central, northern and southern areas of the Buenos Aires Metropolitan Area. With different temporalities and particularities, in all three cases the State, business sectors and real estate agents promote conversions of spaces that are contested and negotiated by popular and media sectors; and they express, as a whole, how the greening of urban policies results in processes of territorial accumulation.

(a) The urban renewal of a "waterfront" in the municipality of Vicente López

Vicente López is a municipality located north of the City of Buenos Aires. In 2004, the authorities of the municipality of Vicente López modified the Urban Planning Code (hereinafter, COU) in order to enable the construction of dozens of high-rise buildings in the riverside area, in the vicinity of a large public park of 44 hectares. Among them, the "Al Río" mega-complex stands out, a monumental real estate project made up of a large shopping center mall, housing towers for a segment of high level of consumption and offices of leading companies. The foregoing represented the transfer of a total of 140 hectares for real estate projects, equivalent to 4% of the territory of Vicente López.

The modification of the Vicente López COU responded, among other factors, to the depletion of construction capacity in the northern zone of the neighboring City of Buenos Aires around 2010, extending the demand for developable land to adjacent areas. Investors, developers and real estate businessmen have directed their attention, since then, towards the municipality of Vicente López, particularly towards its coastal area. The presence of the Río de la Plata and wide extensions of green spaces, added to a low construction density and proximity to the City of Buenos Aires are among the comparative advantages for real estate capital.

Both the business discourse and the local and provincial state aimed to build an "environmentally friendly" image to legitimize urban interventions in the coastal zone, which at first were highly resisted by local citizens. Various actors participated in the construction of this green imaginary: market research companies, marketing agencies, urban planners, organizations that develop sustainability measurement systems, as well as the media, using green marketing statements as arguments. The particular case of the company Al Río holds a LEED certification (acronym for Leader in Energy Efficiency and Sustainable Design), which is granted to constructions that respect certain guidelines such as efficiency in the use of water, energy consumption and energy efficiency. use of materials that care for the environment . Notwithstanding the foregoing, residents mobilized against these urban renewal works denounce that the impact of Al Río and other constructions on the riverside environment is not so "environmentally friendly." Indeed, the municipality received numerous complaints about the incidence of new homes and offices in the saturation of local public services.

Green marketing and the discourse of sustainability are not limited exclusively to the business sphere: they have also been gaining space in the communication strategy of the municipal government. In 2011, the General Directorate of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) was created, which rewards companies that contribute to the "common good" (Municipality of Vicente López, 2018), with which they regularly organize interventions in the coastal public space, with which the local government aimed to intervene the materiality and image of the coastal zone, as part of the urban renewal and regeneration process, which aspired to reconfigure the public space, questioning the citizens' need for green spaces.

(b) Restoration of the Matanza-Riachuelo Basin - divergences regarding the uses for 'cleared' margins of the Riachuelo and contributors

The restoration of the Matanza-Riachuelo basin in the AMBA arises from a ruling of the Supreme Court of Justice known as "Fallo Mendoza" . Based on it, a series of actions were established that the different governments involved had to resolve and which were established in the Matanza-Riachuelo Basin Sanitation Plan (PISA 2010), which was modified in 2016. Among the lines of action to develop is the relocation of populations settled on the margins of watercourses due to their exposure to environmental risk . These relocation processes brought a series of discussions. In the first place, what would be the distance from the water course that delimits those affected and not affected to relocation. In the case of the Riachuelo, in 2011 Judge Armella ordered the use of a figure present in the Argentine Civil Code known as "tow-path" and which is that space intended for the descent of boats on the margins of the courses of navigable water. In the case of streams, the figure of the "riverbank line" was used, as that

margin that every watercourse needs to overflow naturally. In the first case, the towpath involved 35 meters, in the second, the riverbank line was limited to 15 meters.

However, the relocation policy of the basin, which is ongoing and which has been carried out in more lax times than planned, has the effect of freeing up a space of land that is close to watercourses and that it is not considered suitable for human settlement. The discussion that follows, then, is what to do with that freed space.

This discussion is different in each territory and is linked to the singular composition of actors that are deployed there and the interests at stake. Thus, for example, in the City of Buenos Aires and the municipality of Avellaneda, bordering the city, the cleared space was destined for the construction of a new circulation path that allows people to travel, bordering the Riachuelo, in the direction of the neighborhoods of Barracas and La Boca. Another very different case is that of the Santa Catalina Reserve, which is located in the municipality of Lomas de Zamora. There, the municipality tries to reduce the meters involved in the shore line to gain a few more meters in reserve.

In the particular case of Almirante Brown, there are two experiences to highlight. On the one hand, a settlement located on the banks of Arroyo del Rey is literally within the land of a private enterprise, since the owners of this neighborhood called Adrogué Chico bought land that includes one of the banks of the stream. They are anxiously waiting for the relocation to happen to get those lands back. On the other hand, families from the El Trébol settlement recently relocated. The relocated families consulted what would be the fate of the cleared land since in the area, the previous days, it was rumored that this land would be quickly occupied by new inhabitants who are also in precarious housing situations. Before the municipality began to relocate, the destination that it expressed for the spaces of the liberated streams was that of the creation of “biodiversity green corridors”. However, in the case of El Trébol, the municipal agents simply talked about building a plaza or recreational park, and some residents pointed out the danger of building a playground next to a watercourse.

In short, on the grounds that a portion of the city's territory is unsuitable for human settlement due to exposure to environmental risk, land is released that may have very different uses: roads, more land for a nature reserve, recreational parks or even a portion of land for a private actor. This proliferation of such divergent uses shows that, in some cases, policies based on environmental arguments can favor the deployment of mechanisms for territorial accumulation (as in the case of the private neighborhood mentioned) or, they can promote the creation of more spaces for public use (as in the case of a reserve or recreational park).

(c) A farmers' allotment eradication in the City of Buenos Aires

In 2001, various social sectors began to participate in collective protests known as “cacerolazos” (pot banging) and “neighborhood assemblies” in different public spaces in the Autonomous City of Buenos Aires. One of the most mobilized neighborhoods was Caballito, where some residents expressed concern about the spaces abandoned by the State and proposed the creation of an allotment in the areas surrounding the Sarmiento railway tracks, in which it was planned to create a “green corridor” which never came to fruition. The proposal was consolidated and became known in the neighborhood as a project seeking to educate residents regarding the organic bases and the affective relationship that was generated by doing agriculture without pesticides in the city.

During the allotment's period of splendor (2005 - 2006), in some cases, the farmers proposed to “spray” the socioeconomic system with very concrete actions; for example, the rejection of the purchase of land, tools and even seeds. In other cases, the work atmosphere that was generated within the property demonstrated the capacity for autonomy that human beings have when they produce their own food. At that time, the activity was tolerated by the surrounding community in order to contain an economic crisis that was also social and political.

However, over time, the physical appropriation of that urban territory that for some represented “desire and pleasure” (interview with a former gardener, 2008), for others it was “filth and waste”. Some neighborhood residents used stereotypes related to skin color, smell and clothing to describe those who walked around the property. The group of gardeners was thought of as a socially and generationally homogeneous group, without considering that the participants had different occupations, forms of human and social capital and personal trajectories. These stigmatizing narratives, along with the invocation of hygienic-environmental issues, legitimized the eviction of the property in 2009.

If we stick to the events, in 2005 city government officials publicly tendered the remodeling of the property to build a plaza. In 2006 the work was awarded to a private company and in 2007 a sign was installed announcing the expansion of the works towards the site where the crops had been planted. Faced with such a scenario, “legal, political and direct action” the allotment’s growers took all paths simultaneously in order to defend it (Indymedia, July 20, 2007). However, although some officials supported the proposal, they never received a response from “a moderately important technician” who formally recognized the existence of the agricultural space (Horizonte Sur Radio Program, September 7, 2008).

In 2008, through a government decree, the authorities stated that the government had to recover the property for the “use and enjoyment of the entire community,” implying that this “community” was well represented by the neighbors who did not approve of the agricultural project on the property. The decree did not prosper due to an appeal presented by the gardeners. However, months later there was an outbreak in different areas of Argentina, with cases of an acute viral disease transmitted to humans by the bite of an *Aedes aegypti* mosquito (Eco-Epidemiology Laboratory of the Faculty of Exact and Natural Sciences, 2009). This fact would change the conflict’s outcome.

When the epidemic entered the City of Buenos Aires, the neighborhood association that had denounced the allotment’s occupation of the property years before sent to the communal authorities a “request for fumigation and removal or emptying of the bathtubs (used as planters)” (Caballito Puede Civil Association, April 2, 2009). Said request would function for definitive vacating of the property, which was seen as a propitious environment –breeding ground– for dengue. In tune with the famous work of Latour (1983) on anthrax, dengue would be instituted as that non-human element through which a few subjects managed to convince an entire population to assert their own interests. On May 18, 2009, the allotment was finally destroyed by police action under the argument of “environmental risk”, giving rise to the construction of a public walkway that, in the words of the growers, finally became a “cement space”. Despite the existence of the principle of free accessibility (Delgado, 2008), the city government –supported by a part of the residents– changed its mind and considered the use of public space with farming inappropriate, making visible what is not should be seen: the politicization of the environment [and multiple environmentalisms].

9.5. Conclusion

The process of real estate valuation of the Vicente López riverside, the eradication of the allotments in the City of Buenos Aires and the relocation of the Matanza-Riachuelo Basin in Almirante Brown are processes that cannot be understood without taking into account that broader situation involving the metropolitan reconfiguration of the metropolitan region of Buenos Aires since the 1990s, which is characterized by the growing role of financial capital, particularly real estate, in the production of urban space.

According to Boltanski and Chiapello (2002), the current accumulation system is incapable of finding its own morality to the logic of insatiable accumulation (which, taken to its ultimate consequences, would lead to self-destruction), for which reason it must “borrow” principles of legitimation from others. At each historical moment, capitalism has known how to reinvent itself, and managed to reformulate its legitimizing principles, based on nodal points to which society assigns importance and with which it judges the correctness of different actions.

One of those neuralgic points has been, for at least forty years, the environment. Thus, in Vicente López, greenery and nature represent surplus value within the real estate sector for the commercialization of residential and office towers built on the riverbank. Established as an object of consumption, the nature promoted by the projects on the riverbank does not constitute a discourse that challenges the whole of society based on collective well-being or a different ecological project, but rather appeals to individual pleasure. In the case of the Matanza Riachuelo basin, the greening process is related to a relocation policy that frees lands unsuitable for human settlement that can have multiple purposes: it can be used for accumulation or for the use of public space. The case of the city of Buenos Aires deals with a policy of eviction of farmers with environmental arguments, where the State accepts certain activities and statements while discarding others, also using environmental elements.

In summary, in this article we present some of the plots of meaning that make up the environmentalization of the social, in general, and of urban policies, in particular, from an ethnographic approach. The possibility of having been there for relatively long periods of time, interviewing, observing and participating, enabled us to understand the particular ways in which "flesh and blood" actors are testing strategies to favor, delay, delay or even reverse mechanisms of territorial accumulation.

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10. CONTESTING EPISTEMIC TENSIONS IN PUBLIC POLICIES: INSIGHTS FROM INDIGENOUS AND AFRO-AMERICAN GROUPS

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This section highlights contradictions and convergences between public policy implementation by government authorities, generally guided by Western approaches to knowledge, rights and territory, and indigenous and Afro epistemologies. A key point of departure is that, despite progressive legal shifts that promote decolonisation and group rights, across the Latin American region public policy and planning practice often still contributes to the dismantling of indigenous and Afro descendant territories, identities, and knowledge by favouring territorial accumulation dynamics, including mining interventions, maritime development, violent conflict, deforestation, infrastructure projects, and peri-urban land conversions. Indigenous peoples and Afro descendant populations, however, should not be conceived of as passive victims as they continue to actively challenge territorial accumulation through a multiplicity of tactics, ranging from direct action such as strikes or marches to the development of alternative forms of inhabiting, managing and governing territory. The territorial struggles of indigenous and Afro populations, while often silenced and suppressed, have in many instances led to the ratification of new policies that, among others, confront the material and symbolic dimensions of territorial accumulation, harmonise Western and indigenous legal traditions, and call for principles of co-existence, inclusion, and recognition. In the remainder of the text, we focus our discussion on two broader themes – (1) policy and planning practices that seek to “fix” and “displace” indigenous peoples from specific territories and related counter-responses and (2) the emergence of new policies that respond directly to indigenous and Afro descendent struggles – that shed further light on epistemic tensions and efforts to overcome those. We will then provide a tentative outline for a possible programme for future comparative research and knowledge exchange before concluding with a list of relevant public policies.

10.1. Moving beyond approaches that “fix” and “displace” indigenous peoples

Throughout Latin America policy and planning practice continues reproducing ethno-spatial imaginaries rooted in colonialism that draw on Western understandings of spatially bounded and fixed territories (see also Elden 2003), as well as on Hispanic models of blood politics that spatially distinguish between cities as “modern” spaces associated with “white” citizens and the “indigenous” countryside associated with native populations who are granted relative autonomy but denied citizenship, land, and subsoil rights (Horn 2019; Ugarte, Fontana and Caulkins 2017). As we illustrate through several case studies, such public policy representations often serve to advance specific territorial accumulation practices; they also stand in sharp contrast with the lived realities of indigenous peoples themselves. Below, we reflect on some case studies from Bolivia, Chile and Ecuador that we will focus on in future activities in this project:

10.1.1. Contesting territorial “fixing” through a multi-local perspective in Bolivia

Bolivia is renowned internationally for its 2009 constitution, which - as a response itself to insurgent indigenous uprisings - calls for decolonising society, and recognises specific indigenous rights for territorial autonomy, prior consultation, and socio-economic and cultural self-determination (Schavelzon 2012). Yet, tensions remain. While indigenous peoples are granted rights to collective tenure and territorial autonomy, Bolivia’s 2009 constitution declares ground and underground resources to be under public ownership, thereby providing a pathway for authorising resource extraction on and below the lands of indigenous peoples (Anthias 2018; Flemmer and Schilling-Vacaflor 2015; McNeish 2013). Meanwhile, urban policy and planning practice fails to apply collective indigenous rights in cities, assuming instead that indigenous people lose their identity through rural-to-urban migration (Horn 2019). Such efforts to “fix” population groups onto certain territories stand in sharp contrast with the lived reality of indigenous peoples which is characterised by continuous mobility. This a phenomenon that to some degree always existed – as is evident in historical research on discontinued territories and vertical archipelagos (Murra 1975) – but is further exacerbated and reshaped by contemporary dynamics of dispossession and displacement induced by territorial accumulation. In ongoing collaborative research with youth representatives from different indigenous nations in Bolivia the Bolivia and Sheffield teams of the Contested Territories network have begun to conceptualise indigenous territoriality through a focus on their mobility patterns.

Contributing to conceptual work on multi-locality and multi-territoriality (Antequera Duran 2010; Haesbert 2013), our findings highlight that territory, from the perspective of indigenous mobility, should be understood as evolving fluidly along a continuum through multiple flows and displacements, whereby indigenous people circulate between rural and urban places, and move across boundaries and scales. Crucially, our findings suggest that urban and metropolitan spaces represent important support points (most indigenous peoples access public services such as healthcare and education, and engage in economic trade in these places) and central organisational and cultural nodes (most indigenous movements have their political seat in cities from where they engage in struggles affecting their extended territories) in the wider territorial network of indigenous groups. This is evident, for example, for the Qhara Qhara nation, an indigenous Quechua group, whose territories are located in rural, peri-urban and urban areas in the departments of Chuquisaca and Potosi. From their organisational seat in Bolivia’s capital Sucre, this indigenous nation engages in struggles against the dispossession and fragmentation of their territories, demanding instead their constitutional right for territorial autonomy and self-governance by creatively combining engagements with international organisations such as the Interamerican Court of Human Rights (involving mobilisation of Western legal models) and the revitalisation of ancestral knowledge on territorial governance. In doing so, members of the Qhara Qhara nation introduce a decolonial perspective towards territory that recognises the multiple and simultaneous presences of indigenous peoples in a diversity of places that transcend rural-urban as well as departmental boundaries in Bolivia.

10.1.2. The emergence urban indigenous territories in Ecuador’s Amazonia

In Ecuador, issues of indigenous territorial rights must be understood in relation to land reform policies, with the first one being the 1937 “Ley de Comunas” that granted indigenous residents living and working on former colonial haciendas with land rights (Rayner and Mérida Conde, 2019). Further land reforms occurred in the 1960s and 1970s, and indigenous land rights have been granted in the Amazon region especially after large-scale mobilisations that culminated in the 1992 march from the Amazonian city Puyo to Quito (Cubillo-Guevara & Hidalgo-Capitán, 2015).

Ecuador’s government, hence, recognised some of the territorial claims of indigenous peoples but in such a way that indigenous territorial sovereignty is confined to specific spaces while non-existent in other settings, especially in cities as these are considered to be non-indigenous spaces, centres of capitalist production, and governed along Western individual rights.

Indigenous disputes that occur in or seek to claim urban space are branded illegitimate by national and local governments.

An illustration of clashes between government authorities and indigenous communities is the case of Puyo. In this Amazonian city indigenous communities occupied territories. Here, they have established their own governance authority and collective land management regime; they also realise cultural activities that foreground ancestral knowledge and practices, and promote community-led tourist enterprises. Government authorities consider such indigenous urban territorial practices as illegal and declare local indigenous communities as invaders, despite the fact that these territories are situated on areas claimed illegally by the state itself less than 100 years ago (Bayón, 2021). The government certainly makes efforts to accommodate indigenous residents, for example by seeking to grant individual tenure rights to community members. Yet, such efforts are characterised by a colonial and Western logic of urban governance that seeks to dismantle or “whiten” indigenous governance logics through the logic of “integration”, often with the underlying aim to subsume community logics and foster territorial accumulation in areas considered to be viable for real estate projects catering for middle class people from Ecuador’s highlands interested in buying second homes (Bayón, 2021).

10.1.3. Planning for co-existence in urban Chile

In recent years, urbanisation processes in Chile are characterised by complex contestations between different territorial ontologies that go beyond state forms of territorial planning and challenge dominant colonial urban-rural and indigenous-nonindigenous dichotomies (Mansilla & Imilan, 2020). In conceptual terms, the notion of “planning for coexistence” (Porter & Barry, 2016) opens the possibility of discussing territorial planning and the categories that sustain it to a perspective of coexistence of various models of land management based on histories, practices and future projects that go beyond the current frameworks of territorial planning.

In this way, a series of daily practices are observed that produce spatialities that challenge territorial planning, either in the form of resistance or through formulation of alternative territorial projects. We are particularly interested in exploring spatial practices of Mapuche communities in the commune of Padre Las Casas, Araucanía Region, which have been besieged by urban expansion and associated threats of expulsion because of the construction of housing complexes. In the Region of Copiapó, settlements of the Chango people located on the edge of the sea must deal with the settlement of hundreds of houses of irregular form that use bays and beaches as places of recreation, besieging the residential habitat of Changos communities. In the same region, the formation of new Diaguitas and Collas indigenous communities occurs through land occupations and self-managed community projects in desert landscapes on the outskirts of the city. Such practices are viewed by state policies through the prism of informal occupations. These current situations highlight the narrowness of territorial conceptions of both urban and territorial planning policies, but also of indigenous policies themselves, that reproduce the colonial urban/rural binary. In future work, we are interested in critically and comparatively analysing housing policies and urban planning instruments and their implications for indigenous communities in urban or urbanising settings.

10.1.4. Public policies associated with nature conservation: exclusion, inequality and commodification in Southern Chile

Under scientific rationalism, nature is understood as an external object and subjected to processes of domination. In the contemporary juncture we can note how discourses that advance nature conservation dominate public debate on a planetary scale. The historical roots of conservation have been based on moralistic and dualistic arguments in the scientific community about the intrinsic value of nature in terms of the rights and needs of future generations. In Chile, public conservation policies are linked to the creation of parks and nature reserves managed by the State in partnership with private capital, restricting and regulating their use and usufruct. These environmental policies privatize the commons, through concessions or transfer

of rights that often generate environmental damage and difficulties in accessing beaches, rivers and lakes. Many of these national parks are ancestral territories of indigenous peoples, with these groups often threatened by displacement.

Public policy also encourages the creation of private reserves for conservation purposes. These processes are particularly intense in southern Chile, home to territories of high ecological value whose conservation is a priority for the planet. In many places we can observe the development of tourist enclaves and private conservation projects, often with the purpose of advancing territorial accumulation, leading to the displacement and social exclusion of indigenous and peasant communities.

10.2. Promoting policies that problematise Western legal traditions and confront territorial accumulation

Especially in the Colombian context our group notes the emergence of alternative public policies, often the result of struggles by Afro-Colombian and indigenous groups, whose main aim it is to confront practices that justify territorial accumulation and resolve violent social conflicts around the inequitable redistribution of land and resources. Below, we briefly reflect on three of these policies as well as their strengths and limitations:

10.2.1. Law 70: convergences and contradictions with AfroColombian communities in the Pacific region

In the wake of Colombia's 1991 constitutional reform, which recognised for the first time the country's multi-ethnic character, Law 70 was formulated in 1993. The law established a judicial process to provide collective titles to Afro-descendant communities for rural territories which they occupy and use for traditional productive activities. It was preceded by Transitory Article 55, which was passed in 1991 alongside the new constitution, promising Afro-Colombian collective land rights in the Pacific region, along with protection of their cultural identity and rights, and promotion of their economic and social development. The law recognized the historic tenure of Black communities over river basins in the Pacific region and established the figure of communal councils (*consejos comunitarios*) through which communities could organize and govern themselves.

Amid the optimism of the early 1990s, Law 70 seemed to offer the possibility of visibility, rights and political recognition to Afro-descendant communities across the Pacific region and in Colombia more widely. Instrumental in and strengthened by this process was the *Proceso de Comunidades Negras*, a network of social organizations in the Pacific region based in Buenaventura, with more than 20 years of history of articulating Afro-Colombian communities' demands for political, territorial, ecological and cultural autonomy (Escobar, 2014; see also Oslender, 2004, 2016). By 2008, 5 million hectares of land had been assigned via 132 collective land titles in the Pacific region (Agnew & Oslender, 2013). Importantly, this process of collective titling also granted *consejos* the right to *consulta previa* or consultation prior to permission being given for development on their land (alongside any other measures that might affect communities' social, cultural or economic integrity), suggesting an important protective role against territorial accumulation processes.

However, despite the historical achievement that Law 70 represents in Colombia, observers suggest that it has failed to live up to its promise, particularly relating to Afro-Colombian movements' claims around identity and territory (Oslender, 2016). Between constitutional debates and the law's formalization, these claims were diluted, and the category of territory was replaced by 'collective land ownership' based on the distribution of empty or unused land (*tierras baldías*) for collective titling, rather than redistribution (Restrepo, 2013, p. 95). Additionally, the incorporation of the local communities' forms of organisation, framed as 'ethnic-territorial organisations' and recognised in Law 70, ultimately resulted in the diluted figure of *consejos comunitarios*, which are elected and are responsible for governing collective territory, but have ultimately become another actor alongside the state in contesting 'overlapping territorialities'

(Oslender in Cairo 2018). Finally, the right to consulta previa often remains an afterthought, and communities' views are either overlooked completely, or subsumed to other interests.

10.2.2. Public Policy on Communication of and for Indigenous Peoples (PPCPI)

This public policy, ratified in 2018, seeks to address the negative impact that traditional media has on the social valuation of indigenous peoples through the realization and promotion of practices of autonomous communication defined as the creation, production and dissemination of content made by indigenous people.

Its relationship with territorial accumulation lies in the fact that for Colombian indigenous communities the creation of alternative media constitutes a strategic complement to their territorial struggles (Tobar-Tovar and Rodríguez, 2020). For this reason, the dissemination of autochthonous content is proposed to make visible expectations of cultural recognition, economic redistribution and political representation, which are articulated with contemporary demands such as environmental justice and peacebuilding.

Despite a series of difficulties (e.g., lack of training, limited access to equipment), some indigenous peoples have managed to advance in their communication efforts by taking a critical stance against discriminatory conceptions of the indigenous. Some emblematic examples are found in the department of Cauca through the processes carried out by the organization Tejido de Comunicación of the Association of Indigenous Councils of Northern Cauca, ACIN (Nasa people). On the other hand, on the Atlantic Coast, the Zhigoneshi Collective of the Gonawindúa Tayrona Organization of the Sierra Nevada de Santa Marta (Wiwa, Kogui and Arhuaco peoples).

In the case of Valle del Cauca, we find an initial community-led process that seeks to replicate lessons from other national and international indigenous communities and apply it to the local context. The Javeriana Cali University seeks to support these efforts.

10.2.3. Public Policy Cali Afro

This policy issued by the municipal government of Cali focuses on the black, Afro-Colombian, raizales and palenqueras communities (hereinafter BARP) that inhabit this city. It aims to address specific problems (especially linked to violence) experienced by these groups, putting emphasis on their recognition and representation in public spaces (Agreement 0459 of 2019). It emerged in 2021 as a response to a series of events, including the national strike occurring this year but also neighbourhood campaigns in the barrio Charco Azul occurring since 2002 as well as the massacre of five young people from the Llano Verde neighbourhood in 2020 that brought into light the negative implications of forced displacement. Problems the policy seeks to address are lack of education, multi-dimensional poverty, precarious housing, and the failure to address the specific territorial and group rights of BARP. The relationship of this policy with territorial accumulation lies in the fact that the experience of the Colombian armed conflict has a special effect on the way in which the uses of the territory in the countryside and the city are signified. Many BARP communities inhabit the District of Aguablanca and identify themselves as victims of violence. While only recently ratified, the policy will provide a good case study to understand how the concerns of Afro-Colombian communities are addressed in practice.

10.3. Synthesis and next steps

In this section we highlighted important tensions between public policies guided by Western legal discourses, and often promoting territorial accumulation, and indigenous and Afro-descendent epistemologies and lived experiences. We also highlighted how public policies are not static but often subject to resistance and modification. Our discussion on indigenous and Afro struggles against territorial accumulation and related public policies highlights two important, interrelated and often simultaneously applied, trends: First, some activist practices

seek to address indigenous and Afro claims within dominant governance systems, for example by developing laws and policies within the tradition of Western legal discourse, by aligning their claims to domestic or international indigenous rights legislation, or by suggesting inter-legal proposals that seek to combine insights of Western legal discourse with indigenous cosmopolitanism. Second, other activist practices promote autonomous territorial governance systems and call for rights to co-exist with more conventional policies and governance configurations. What these different practices share in common is an effort to confront territorial accumulation and related threats to indigenous and Afro ways of living.

While there exist similar trends in the countries in which our working group members are based and/ or work collaboratively with indigenous and Afro activists, there is a need for more cross-cultural comparison, learning and exchange. As working group we therefore plan to develop a B1 project that focuses on facilitating a series of cross-cultural dialogues on coping with and confronting territorial “fixing”, “displacement” and “accumulation” through involving first and foremost youths (the future of indigenous and Afro descendant socio-territorial movements) from communities with whom we already have strong collaborative partnerships. As a preparatory step, and to inform our B1 application to be prepared in 2023, we will undertake a series of preliminary conversations in the coming months with selected young people to identify their priorities in relation to territorial accumulation and related policy responses as well as ideas on how to address these issues as part of a collaborative research project within the Contested Territories network. We will consolidate insights from these interviews into podcasts to be shared with youth participants based in different territories as well as network members. The proposed activities align with work packages 3 (Documenting and Visualising Contested Territories) and 4 (Connecting and Reclaiming Contested Territories) and will feed into relevant project outputs, including the Atlas of Territorial Accumulation.

10.4. Primary policy sources

Bolivian constitution (2009): <https://www.lexivox.org/norms/BO-CPE-20090207.xhtml>

Ley INRA (1998): <https://www.lexivox.org/norms/BO-RE-DS24784.xhtml>

Ley de hidrocarburos (2005): <http://extwprlegs1.fao.org/docs/pdf/bol52651.pdf>

Ley marco de autonomías y descentralización ‘Andrés Ibáñez’ (2010): <https://www.lexivox.org/norms/BO-L-N31.xhtml>

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11- POPULAR MARKETS, CONSUMPTION CIRCUITS AND FOOD PRODUCTION.

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The production, distribution, circulation and consumption of food and other goods is intimately linked to processes of territorial accumulation and dispossession that develop geographically and socially unevenly. The working group for popular trade and markets analyses processes that range from the commodification and neoliberalization of these circuits by the State and private interests to alternative practices and resistance that aim to decommodify and recognise their social value. In particular, we focus on how these uneven processes are territorialised creating injustices across rural and urban settings but also how alternatives emerge from these territories.

11.1 Main theoretical contributions

Food is a contested arena in which different actors, capitals, interests, discourses, tensions and a diversity of strategies come together. Critical agri-food studies have focused in particular on how the production, distribution and access to food are part of a global capitalist regime (Bernstein, 2016) accelerating processes of industrialisation, standardisation and (neo)colonial relationships between countries and across other scales.

Contestation has broadened to include not only access and distribution, but has also taken a turn towards quality; a concept that brings together aspects such as nutrition, the importance of food “provenance” and socio-technical processes of food production. Murdoch et al. (2000) explain that this shift stems from the effect of globalization on the food sector, taking as a reference its industrialization and commodification in parallel to a concentration of the capital that produces and distributes food.

The changes in the circulation of food do not only have an impact on the economic dimension; but also on their general territorial relations. In Seale’s (2016: 12) study of marketplaces she conceives them as nodes where material and intangible flows – of people, goods, time, senses, affections – circulate, end, are transformed or directly pass. This relational approach puts the emphasis on the links and relations between participating agents; who are tied up in uneven networks of power. Thinking of food spaces and territories in a dynamic sense rather than as fixed, leads us to notice the circulation of food as contingent on these social relations.

Debates within this field have also focused on the alternatives and resistance to the corporate and capitalist food systems. Within this framework, the emergence and articulation of consumer and producer organizations, allied with various institutions, has been documented, generating alternative circuits and systems for the production and circulation of food with distinctive quality traits that gave rise to "alternative food geographies" (Whatmore, Thorne 1997). In the Anglo-Saxon context, these networks (Alternative Food Networks - AFNs) were understood from their reactive nature to the conventional agri-food system (Murdoch, et al 2000) while other authors emphasized the influence of social movements in the promotion of local community experiences for the social and economic sustainability of families (Migliore, et al 2019).

There are many other areas of debate and theoretical discussion linked to the ecological crisis, racism and feminism.

The production and distribution of food and other consumption goods is a pillar of capitalism and as such it is a fundamental arena for territorial accumulation and dispossession. At the heart of the emergence of capitalism there was the land grabbing and expulsion of peasants from common land, where they could provision themselves with food. More recently, the expansion of soy production in Latin American land to feed animals and the production of super-processed foods, can be seen as a new form of extractivism. Corporate-led food production and distribution is very energy dependent thus contributing to the current world-ecology crisis.

The production and distribution of food and other consumption goods has at its center labor power: from slave labor in plantations, women unpaid farm work to precarious workers in the food industry, in bars and restaurants in gentrified neighborhoods or traveling through streets delivering fast food.

In urban contexts we find that food access and distribution is another profit making frontier. Corporate retailers crowd out central urban spaces displacing small and often family-run neighborhood businesses. At the same time, boutique-style, high-end food businesses lead or reinforce processes of touristification and gentrification displacing or pricing out low income residents who have to rely on cheap and highly processed food or travel long distances to access food.

11.2 Mechanisms of territorial accumulation in the case studies

The markets and popular retail working group aims to ask the following questions in their research: What role or roles do state agencies assume in the matter of food? Which subjects do they promote and which others condition? In which cases do they stay on the sidelines, intentionally omit regulations? What role do alternative food production have in the resistance or further commodification of food systems?

Below, we present three cases that allow us to account for these concerns.

In the United Kingdom, traditional retail markets emerged in the 19th c. as pioneering state municipal centers for food safety and also the disciplining of the working class food consumption and shopping habits. But by the 21st century various global and urban processes have led to their marginalization (Taylor and Gonzalez, forthcoming). In the UK, the supermarketization process has led to the absolute power of very few supermarket chains who control the grocery market and who have become financialised institutions investing in banking, insurance or housing. In the 1990s, neoliberal Thatcherite policies promoted out of town and car-based shopping centers which led to the decline of town and urban centers where most traditional retail markets are based. The mass incorporation of women to the labor market, particularly since the 2WW also changed home food provisioning patterns; relying more on highly processed foods provided conveniently by supermarkets who have long opening hours, based on cheap labor. More recently, the rise of delocalised internet retailers relying on cheap distribution, manufacturing, warehouse and delivery labor has further marginalized traditional retail markets. Added to these trends, these markets tend to be owned and managed by local authorities which particularly since the 2008 crisis have suffered crippling public fund cuts.

In the UK, traditional markets are not considered, as in other countries, public services; Instead they are generally regarded as income generating commercial properties. There are around 1,000 of these markets in towns and cities across the UK. There is no national public policy regarding markets; at local level, markets are often linked strategically to public policies but their public role is fragmented nationally and hence diminished and overlooked. As public funding continues to be reduced, markets have become important tools for local councils to generate income. This seems to take two approaches: either selling or leasing out the market to private operators for a profit or investing public money in the market to regenerate it and attract new customers to generate further municipal income (Gonzalez and Waley, 2013). In either case, the community value that markets generate in terms of access to affordable food but also as spaces of social interaction particularly for low income groups, tends to be forgotten or dismissed (Gonzalez, et al, 2021). This can lead to the displacement of these groups when markets become regenerated. But markets are contested urban spaces and there have been citizen and trader campaigns to save them from decline, demolition, privatization of gentrification. In particular, in London markets that served minoritised and working class groups have seen strong campaigns linking customers and traders and highlighting the community aspects of these spaces (Gonzalez and Dawson, 2017).

In the case of Madrid, the transformations of the markets are part of the development plans that are committed to the insertion of the city in the global tourist and financial market, building a competitive image of Madrid with international projection. As a consequence of these local public policies, its municipal markets become disputed territories due to the processes of commercial gentrification and touristification in two spatial areas: the gentrified neighborhoods of the central almond of the city and, in general, in the food markets. municipally owned. In these processes, traditional retail stores are displaced by high-status gourmet establishments, aimed at serving the transient tourist population and competing for an urban middle class that has opted for supermarkets as the preferred supply modality.

From the government and business perspective, supply markets are represented as deteriorated places. The generation of this discourse justifies its rescue and the subsequent rediscovery of its commercial and urban value. In this line, the reforms of the municipal markets carried out by the local governments of Madrid incorporate new functions under the premise of "modernizing and updating them". The interest in turning municipal markets into a competitive commercial format, integrated and adapted to new consumption habits, led to the implementation from 2003 to 2011 of the I Plan for Innovation and Transformation of Madrid Municipal Markets, (City Hall of Madrid, 2003). Said Plan, considered a success, was extended for the period 2012-2015, with emphasis on marketing and advertising of the Mercados de Madrid brand, on the modernization of the physical and commercial structure and finally on the search for professionalization and improvement of its management. Lastly, in the 2017-2021 period, the Madrid Municipal Markets Strategic Plan was developed, which focuses on the physical remodeling of buildings and applying management models typical of large companies with the aim of increasing profitability. These objectives are contradictory to the social function of the markets as centers of neighborhood coexistence and do not take into account social and cultural factors of their operation and their historical role in the urban environment.

Another axis of municipal policy has consisted in modifying the regulations that govern the operation of the markets to allow new types of businesses, reducing the percentage of area that must be used for food trade from 65% to 35% (Ayuntamiento de Madrid, 2014), and establishing that up to 40% of the common space could be used for events, such as tastings. This regulation favors the reorganization of the stalls into a "traditional" part and an "innovative" part, and the gradual displacement of food product sales stalls in favor of restaurant spaces and gourmet stores that are much more profitable.

In summary, the renovation model that is implemented in the municipal markets deepens the transformation of the material space, the type of business, the products they offer, and the public they are intended for, so that the function of the supply market is replaced by leisure, recreation and consumption activities similar to malls, in line with neoliberal commercial and

urban transformation guidelines. Consequently, the markets have been transformed into thematic spaces as nodes of tourist attraction and as spaces of distinction and leisure of a certain middle class.

The neoliberal policies are the same ones that have affected the production concentration markets in Argentina. In the case of public policies that regulated the circulation of fresh food in the city of Buenos Aires, (Law 10202/84) a "monopolistic concentrator market" was created. However, with the advent of neoliberal economic liberalization policies, between 1991 and 1993 this centrality was deregulated (Decree 2284/91), giving rise to the free market that continues to this day

Regulation as a matter is a recurrence in studies about food markets and, in those studies where they are focused on the circuits of production, distribution and consumption. The last proposal that is replaced here follows this trend, but it is a regulation that we can analyze from a margin (Das and Poole, 2008).

This last contribution is focused on a regulation, known as the Participatory Guarantee System (SPG). The SPG is understood as a distinction aimed at recognizing agroecological products. Unlike organic agriculture, which in Argentina has a distinction framed in a National Law, for agroecological production, these processes of state legibility are fully armed, although there are various experiences that point to being able to distinguish this mode of production from above. others. The case we took on is located in the Metropolitan Area of Buenos Aires (AMBA), Argentina, and this process involves producers, consumers and people who make up an extension area of a national public university together with an advisory council made up of other national agencies.

This System is understood herein as a mode of regulation that tends to encourage the participation of different people who make up the production. Unlike other regulations that are established for the distinction of foods such as organic or fair trade, which are recognized by third parties, here is another process that indicates whether or not a product is recognized as agroecological. Trust appears as a central value in this plot, but it does not end there as a series of indicators to be taken into account to make use of this seal of distinction were built from the parts that make up this SPG.

Although in Argentina there are experiences, at least, since the beginning of the 2000s in the practice of Participatory Guarantee Systems (Marcos, 2013), the case we took, located in the AMBA, began with this process in 2018. This occurred within the framework of previous relationships that members of a Food Sovereignty chair at a national university had with a group of agroecological producers with whom they traded bags of vegetables (Demichelli, 2022).

Being part of a SPG appeared as a strategy for these producers who produce food in a unique way but, within marketing networks, even in short circuits, can remain without distinction. Being in the SPG also becomes a guarantee for those who consume, since they can identify, through a seal that displays both in direct sales or in the delivery of bags, a differentiation that indicates a production process that is not only free of synthetic chemicals, but where social, economic and gender aspects are taken into account.

11.3 Preliminary questions

One issue that this experience highlights is the production of regulations that are created not only from state institutions but also appear, in some cases, as demands from those who produce food in order to seek a difference, highlighting positive aspects of the way of production.

At the beginning of this writing we affirmed that food is in a disputed arena. Various actors participate in this dispute, in different positions that affect the ways in which public policies are produced.

We understand public policy in production that is later crystallized in compliance, in bureaucratic management units and in multiple strategies that cross the daily life of the populations.

Food appears as a particularly sensitive subject because it is essential for the reproduction of life, in its commercial sphere we can see, through them, how modes of distinction are expressed.

Within the framework of the policy briefs, we highlight the interest for the popular trade and markets group to reflect on the ways in which regulations (produced from the State, from social organizations, or from other environments) have effects and they shape the way we are producers and consumers.

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12. AFTERWORD

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Territorial accumulation relies heavily on policy mechanisms. The contributions to this working paper have shown why critical policy analysis (CPA) is needed to understand processes whereby the contemporary restructuring of global capitalism hinges on spatial fixes with profound implications for the transformation of territories.

The Contested Territories network is characterised by its ambitious approach to territorial contestation across morphological and regional differences. The CPA contributions to this paper reflect this broad scope and have engaged with urban, rural, and nature geographies across Latin America and Europe whilst also pointing to hybrid configurations at the intersection of economic development, infrastructure provision, social resistances, and ecological processes.

The working paper should be read as work in progress as the contributions were intended both as a summary of discussions to date and roadmap for future research within and across our network's diverse working groups. In particular, we hope that this 'first cut' on the policy mechanisms of territorial accumulation will support the development and be supplemented with the development of future outputs focusing on the concrete policy implications of the territorial contestations covered herein. Moreover, we look forward to the network's innovation on methodologies that may better incorporate 'other knowledges' to the policy process and thereby include interests and perspectives that have been historically excluded such as those of indigenous peoples and Afro-American communities.

As a concluding thought, the cases and examples presented through the section focus on the particular of each policy and contestation to purposely challenge the entrenched notion of 'fast recommendations' in the world of policy consultancy yet also point to common problems and the potential for theorisations across differences that may inform more critical and transformative policy formulations to engage with the territorial dimensions of global capital in crisis.